

Criteria used to measure the quality of news media reports about
the effects of health interventions: Systematic review

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Abstract

Background: There have been many studies of the quality of news media reports about the effects of health interventions, but no review of such studies.

Primary objective: To assess criteria used to measure the quality of news media reports about the effects of health interventions.

Methods: Studies were included if they used at least one explicit, *a priori*, generic criterion to measure the quality of print, broadcast or online reports—i.e. how conducive the reports were to informed decisions. Criteria from those studies were included in the analysis if they were clear and appropriate. Criteria were compared to a comprehensive list of concepts people need to apply to assess information about the effects of health interventions, and make informed decisions. The results of the analysis were used to group the criteria.

Results: Twenty-nine studies were included. Researchers most frequently studied news reports in newspapers, in English-speaking and high-income countries, over the last 20 years, about “modern” medicine or diet (not necessarily reports with all four characteristics).

Twenty tools (sets of criteria) were used in the studies. Two-hundred of 368 individual criteria (54%) were included in the review. Included criteria were placed in 19 groups. There were gaps in the categories of news reports studied, and methodological weaknesses in how quality has been measured. Many criteria required substantial judgement and were unclear, several important aspects of quality were not measured, and some criteria were not sensible.

Implications: Future studies of the quality of health information in the news media, and other media, should consider the findings of this review before selecting a population, and selecting or developing a tool to measure the quality. The results of the planned meta-analysis should be conducted and interpreted with caution due to potential heterogeneity, and other issues with the criteria.

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Background

The problem

This study is a systematic review that is ultimately intended to help address a major, global problem. The problem has three parts; unreliable information about the effects of health interventions; inability to assess such information; and uninformed decisions about health interventions, leading to waste and unnecessary suffering.

Unreliable information about the effects of health interventions

The first part of the problem is that there is endless information about the effects of health interventions, and much of it is unreliable, if not most of it. A health intervention is herein any action intended to improve or maintain the health of individuals or groups. This includes information about: “modern”, “academic”, “conventional” or “western” medicine; “complementary”, “alternative”, “traditional” or “natural” medicine; screening; surgery and devices; diet, exercise and lifestyle; and systems and policies. Information about the effects of these interventions can be directly misleading, such as the explicit claim that an intervention causes an outcome when it is only associated with the outcome. Or, it can be misleading by omission, such as relative risks without absolute risks, particularly when the baseline risk is small (Akl, et al., 2011).

Researchers have found unreliable lay information about the effects of health interventions in advertisements, patient materials, and the news. Out of a sample of 14 print advertisements for non-prescription drugs, Sansgiry et al. found, a majority lacked “adequate” information

about safety (n = 12, 86%) and side effects (n = 13, 93%) (1999, p. 15). Coulter et al. found quantitative information about recovery time and outcome probabilities was missing from “most” of 54 patient materials about treatments (1999, p. 319). And Walsh-Childers et al. found less than a third of news reports assessed between 2005 and 2009 (n = 263, 29%) quantified benefits, as did less than half of those assessed between 2010 and 2013 (n= 369, 39%) (2016).

Inability to assess information about the effects of health interventions

The second part of the problem is that people are unable to assess the reliability of information about the effects of health interventions. Before moving on to the evidence, it is important to define what it means to be able (or unable) to assess such information.

As part of the Informed Health Choices (IHC) project (www.informedhealthchoices.org), the ability to assess information about the effects of health interventions, as well as make informed decisions about health interventions, has been broken down into the ability to apply specific concepts called the IHC Key Concepts (Chalmers, et al., 2018; Austvoll-Dahlgren, et al., 2017). For example, people need to be able to apply the concept that relative risks can be misleading.

The list differs from other resources in how it was developed, and its uses (Chalmers, et al., 2018, pp. 30-31). In terms of its development, it is both: a) developed using a systematic, transparent and iterative process; and b) intended to be relevant to the general public, including children, not just health researchers or professionals. In terms of its uses, unlike resources such as checklists and tip sheets, the IHC Key Concepts list is not an intervention,

limited to a particular population or context. Rather, it is a comprehensive framework that can be used to develop and evaluate interventions and measurement tools.

The newest published iteration of the IHC Key Concept list includes 36 concepts, organized in three groups (Box 1) (Chalmers, et al., 2018). In this review, I also refer to two new IHC Key Concepts from the latest draft iteration of the list (Box 2) (Oxman, et al., [unpublished]). People's ability to apply IHC Key Concepts has been measured both directly and indirectly. In the next part of this subsection, I first discuss the latter.

Box 1: Short titles for the Informed Health Choices (IHC) Key Concepts

Recognising an unreliable basis for a claim

- 1.1. Treatments can harm.
- 1.2. Anecdotes are unreliable evidence.
- 1.3. Association is not the same as causation.
- 1.4. Common practice is not always evidence-based.
- 1.5. Newer is not necessarily better.
- 1.6. Expert opinion is not always right.
- 1.7. Beware of conflicting interests.
- 1.8. More is not necessarily better.
- 1.9. Earlier is not necessarily better.
- 1.10. Hope may lead to unrealistic expectations.
- 1.11. Explanations about how treatments work can be wrong.
- 1.12. Dramatic treatment effects are rare.

Understanding whether comparisons are fair and reliable

- 2.1. Comparisons are needed to identify treatment effects.
- 2.2. Comparison groups should be similar.
- 2.3. Peoples' outcomes should be analysed in their original groups.
- 2.4. Comparison groups should be treated equally.
- 2.5. People should not know which treatment they get.
- 2.6. Peoples' outcomes should be assessed similarly.
- 2.7. All should be followed up.
- 2.8. Consider all the relevant fair comparisons.
- 2.9. Reviews of fair comparisons should be systematic.
- 2.10. Peer review and publication does not guarantee reliable information.
- 2.11. All fair comparisons and outcomes should be reported.
- 2.12. Subgroup analyses may be misleading.
- 2.13. Relative measures of effects can be misleading.
- 2.14. Average measures of effects can be misleading.
- 2.15. Fair comparisons with few people or outcome events can be misleading.
- 2.16. Confidence intervals should be reported.
- 2.17. Do not confuse "statistical significance" with "importance".
- 2.18. Do not confuse "no evidence of a difference" with "evidence of no difference".

Making informed choices

- 3.1. Do the outcomes measured matter to you?
- 3.2. Are you very different from the people studied?
- 3.3. Are the treatments practical in your setting?
- 3.4. Do treatment comparisons reflect your circumstances?
- 3.5. How certain is the evidence?
- 3.6. Do the advantages outweigh the disadvantages?

Box 2: New IHC Key Concepts 2.3a and 3.1a

Concepts	Short titles	Explanations	Implications
2.3a. Verbal descriptions of treatment effects can be misleading.	Just words	A treatment effect (a change in outcomes) is a numerical concept, but it is difficult for some people to understand quantitative information about the effects of treatments. Qualitative (verbal) labels may be easier to understand and can be helpful. However, qualitative descriptions of effects mean different things to different people; e.g. saying that a treatment will ‘slightly reduce’, ‘reduce’, or ‘greatly reduce’ the likelihood of an undesirable outcome; or that a side effect is ‘frequent’ or ‘rare’. In addition, verbal descriptions of treatments can be manipulative; e.g. promising ‘amazing results’ or describing treatments as ‘natural’, implying that they are safe because of that.	A verbal description of a treatment effect can be helpful, but it should be considered together with quantitative information about the size of the effect. Be wary of manipulative use of language in descriptions of treatments.
3.1a. The problem and the treatment options being considered may not be the right ones.	What is your problem and what are your options?	Good decisions depend on correctly identifying the problems and considering an appropriate set of options to address the problems. For personal health choices, this means starting with a correct diagnosis (or assessment of risk) and then identifying the treatments that are available. For public health and health system policy decisions, this means describing the problem correctly and identifying the policy options relevant for that problem. Changing how a problem is framed can lead to different options for addressing it.	Make sure you are considering the correct diagnosis or problem, and appropriate options for treating it.

There have been large surveys of “health literacy”, in Europe by the European Health Literacy Project Consortium (HLS-EU Consortium, 2012), and in the United States by the National Center for Education Statistics (Kutner, et al., 2006). According to the European survey, “Health literacy is linked to literacy and entails people’s knowledge, motivation and competences to access, understand, appraise, and apply health information in order to make judgments and take decisions in everyday life concerning healthcare, disease prevention and health promotion to maintain or improve quality of life during the life course” (p. 7). For the American survey, health literacy was defined as: “The degree to which individuals have the capacity to obtain, process, and understand basic health information and services needed to make appropriate health decisions” (p. iii). By these two definitions, the ability to apply IHC Key Concepts is a component of health literacy. However, neither survey appears to have objectively measured it.

The European survey measured the self-reported ease of 47 tasks. Those related to applying IHC Key Concepts, including, “judge if the information about illness in the media is reliable”, were ranked by participants as being amongst the most difficult (p. 13). The American survey suggested a minority of American adults (12%) had “proficient” health literacy (p. v). However, only a sample of the health literacy questions used in the American survey are publicly available and none of the available questions measure the ability to assess information about causality (www.nces.ed.gov/NAAL/sample.asp).

Another surrogate measure of people’s ability to apply IHC Key Concepts is their expectations about effects. In a systematic review of patients’ expectations, the majority of participants overestimated benefits and underestimated harms (Hoffmann & Del Mar, 2015).

A systematic review of clinicians' expectations showed clinicians do the same (Hoffmann & Del Mar, 2017).

Other surrogates for ability are attitudes, and other beliefs (besides self-efficacy). According to a study in the United Kingdom, patients and general practitioners appear to place a disproportionate amount of trust in the reputation of the organization conducting a clinical trial, the qualifications of the researchers, and peer-review, versus the methods, which are what in fact determine the reliability of the results (The Academy of Medical Sciences, 2014). Moreover, only about a third of the respondents (37%) placed a high level of trust in data from medical trials, while about two thirds (65%) placed a high level of trust in the experiences of friends and family, i.e. anecdotal evidence.

Moving on to research that directly measured people's ability to apply IHC Key Concepts, in Norway, Oxman et al. tested a random sample of 626 Norwegian adults (2017). About one in five (19%) showed they understood that association does not necessarily imply causation. Other surveys showed Norwegian students in post-secondary school (Pettersen, 2007) and secondary school (Pettersen, 2005) also struggle with assessing claims about the effects of treatments.

Another product of the Informed Health Choices project is the CLAIM Evaluation Tools database (www.informedhealthchoices.org/claim-evaluation-tools). The database contains multiple-choice questions developed specifically to measure people's ability to apply the IHC Key Concepts (Austvoll-Dahlgren, et al., 2017; Austvoll-Dahlgren, et al., 2017). A validated set of 26 questions from the database, measuring the ability to apply 13 of the IHC Key

Concepts (i.e. two questions per concept) were used to measure the effects of IHC learning resources in two randomised trials.

In the first trial, there were data for 4430 Ugandan primary school children in the control group (Nsangi, et al., 2017). In the second trial, there were data for 273 adults in the control group (Semakula, et al., 2017). Less than half of the participants in the control group for either trial answered both questions correctly for any of the 13 included concepts.

Uninformed decisions about health interventions

The combination of unreliable information about the effects of health interventions and people's inability to assess such information can result in uninformed decisions, which is the third part of the problem. People acting on unreliable information, or failing to act on reliable information, can lead to waste and unnecessary suffering, which is why the problem is important.

In a systematic review, low health literacy was found to be associated with worse health outcomes (Berkman, et al., 2011). However, not all of the included studies measured people's objective ability to assess information about the effects of health interventions, i.e. apply IHC Key Concepts. Certainly, people are making poor decisions. Studies have found: worldwide overuse of medical services more likely to do harm than good (Brownlee, et al., 2017); underuse of effective services (Glasziou, et al., 2017); and over-testing and under-testing in primary care (O'Sullivan, et al., 2018).

Meanwhile, fortunes are spent on “alternative” medicine and dietary supplements, despite a lack of reliable evidence demonstrating benefit or safety (Optum, 2013; Starr, 2015). The inability to apply IHC Key Concepts is logically a contributor to this waste.

This study

What is this study?

This study is a systematic review of criteria used to measure (assess) the quality of news media reports about the effects of health interventions. “Quality” is defined herein as how conducive information is to informed decisions about health interventions, or how misleading it is. An aspect of quality is for example whether absolute risks are presented. A criterion is a standard of quality that can be satisfied or not, e.g. the criterion that absolute risks are presented.

There have been several primary studies measuring the quality of news reports about the effects of health interventions—i.e. studies where researchers have taken a sample of such reports and measured the quality of the reports by applying a set of criteria (using a tool). However, as described in my protocol, I was unable to find a review of such studies (Appendix 1).¹

¹Note that the first two appendices to the protocol are attached to this dissertation, together with the protocol. I have only included the first two appendices because they are the only ones with content that I reference directly in the dissertation. To not reveal my name, I have removed the first two pages of the protocol, and do not provide the citation for the Prospero record.

The protocol, which was registered in Prospero, includes two primary analyses: a methodological analysis of the different criteria used to measure quality in different primary studies; and a meta-analysis of results from those studies. For this dissertation, I have conducted the former. Separating the meta-analysis from my dissertation was a pragmatic decision. It allowed more time for the methodological analysis, as well as more space to describe it and put it in context.

Why focus on news media reports?

The news media play a special role in the dissemination of health information. For example, in the United Kingdom, despite an increase in the use of social media, a majority of adults still find out about science most regularly through news media, according to a representative survey of 1,749 adults (Castell, et al., 2014). Meanwhile, Chew and Eysenbach found that in 5395 tweets about the H1N1 outbreak in 2009, the largest proportion of links (23%) were to a news website (2010). Another 12% linked to news blogs, feeds or niche news, compared to 2% that linked to government and public health agencies.

While there are other important sources of lay information about the effects of health interventions, including them in this review would be “mixing apples and oranges”. For example—although there may be overlap—it may not make sense to use the exact same criteria to measure the quality of both news reports prepared by non-health professionals on short deadlines, and patient materials prepared by health professionals.

Furthermore, including sources besides the news media could make the review unwieldy. As stated in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions, there are pros and

cons to both broad and narrow review questions, but with the advent of overviews of systematic reviews, “It may increasingly be considered desirable to plan a series of reviews with a relatively narrow scope, alongside an Overview to summarize their findings” (Higgins & Green, 2011).

Why review criteria used to measure quality?

In 2017, Zeraatkar et al. conducted a literature search before developing their own tool to measure the quality of reporting on health research, named the Quality Index for health-related Media Reports (QIMR). They identified one other validated tool with the same purpose, named the Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ) (Oxman, et al., 1993). They also identified and assessed two instruments for measuring the quality of patient information—Ensuring Quality Information for Patients (EQIP) (Moult, et al., 2004) and DISCERN (Charnock, et al., 1999) (Charnock, et al., 1999)—which they concluded have poor content relevance to health news reports.

As explained in my protocol, it would be problematic to use only the QIMR or ISQ in a systematic review of studies measuring the quality of news media reports about the effects of health interventions, for several reasons. First of all, either scope would be too narrow, since they exclude reports where the health information is not based on research (e.g. information based on expert opinion or anecdotal evidence). At the same time, either scope would be too broad, since they include reports that are not about the effects of interventions (e.g. reports about the effects of exposures).

Second, studies using non-validated tools would be excluded, but a criterion does not have to be validated to help achieve the objective of this review. Third, before finalising the protocol for this review, I was only aware of one independent study using either the QIMR or the ISQ (Lewis, et al., 2010), while I was aware of 41 others I thought might be eligible for inclusion (Appendix 1).

Therefore, in this review, I included studies in which researchers have measured the quality of reports about the effects of health interventions using both validated and non-validated tools. I extracted descriptive data, assessed the different tools and individual criteria, mapped the criteria against the IHC Key Concepts, and grouped individual criteria informed by the results of the mapping. The findings have important implications for future primary studies and for the aforementioned, planned meta-analysis.

The descriptive data provide an overview that can inform further research regarding the quality of health information in the news media, as well other mass media, such as social media. In other words, it can inform future research regarding the first part of the problem laid out in the beginning of the background section, making sure new studies have clear objectives, and fill gaps in the research, rather than be redundant. The descriptive data reveal:

- what populations of news reports have been studied, in terms of medium, country, and time period, and the category of intervention subject to reporting;
- what the stated study objectives have been, and what sampling frames (sources of news reports), and selection criteria and techniques have been used; and
- what factors have been used for subgroup analyses.

Assessing the tools and individual criteria, and mapping the included criteria against the IHC Key Concepts will reveal: which tools have been evaluated and how; what criteria are sensible measures of quality, as I have defined it; which aspects of quality have been measured, typically or at all; and differences between criteria in terms of how much judgement it requires to apply them, and how clear it is what they are measuring. These findings can inform the selection or development of tools for future primary studies.

Finally, assessing and grouping the criteria is a crucial first step towards a reliable and meaningful synthesis of results. It suggests which criteria should be included in the planned meta-analysis, which can be combined, and where there may be heterogeneity. The planned meta-analysis can in turn help address the problem described at the beginning of the background section in at least two ways. It can raise awareness about the problem, and stimulate initiatives to address it. And it can inform the prioritization of IHC Key Concepts when developing interventions to help journalists produce reliable and informative reports, or help consumers assess information in the news and other mass media, by revealing the criteria that news reports most frequently fail to satisfy.

Objectives

My primary objective was to assess criteria used to measure the quality of news media reports about the effects of health interventions. Secondary objectives were; to provide a descriptive overview of studies that have measured the quality of news media reports about health interventions, including gaps in the research; and to provide the basis for summarising the findings of those studies in a planned meta-analysis.

Methods

Eligibility

I included primary studies in this review where researchers used at least one explicit, *a priori*, generic criterion to measure the quality of print, broadcast and online news media reports about the effects of health interventions. Studies had to satisfy three other eligibility criteria: two related to the population of news reports; and one eligibility criterion related to the reporting of study details. The criteria are listed in Box 3. I expand on them in the following subsections of the review. Studies had to be in English or Norwegian, for pragmatic reasons. I did not set any limits on when studies were published.

Box 3: Eligibility criteria for primary studies to be included in this review

Population

Eligibility Criterion 1: The sample includes reports labelled by the researchers as news, published in newspapers or magazines, on television, radio or podcasts, or on news websites.

Eligibility Criterion 2: The sample includes reports about the effects of health interventions.

Study design

Eligibility Criterion 3: At least one explicit, *a priori*, generic criterion was used to measure the quality of the reports.

Reporting

Eligibility Criterion 4: The sampling frame, and the selection criteria and technique are specified.

Eligibility Criterion 1 (population)

As explained in the protocol, “news” is difficult to define. Therefore, instead of using a specific definition, I considered reports as news if they were labelled by the authors as news. Reports had to be published a medium pre-specified in the protocol: newspapers and magazines (print); radio, podcasts or television (broadcast); and news websites (online).

I have only included studies of dedicated news websites, although news reports do appear other places online, for example on social media platforms. This was again to avoid “mixing apples and oranges”. I did not set limits on where in the world or when the news reports were published. However, limiting the review to studies in English or Norwegian made it less likely that I would include news reports in other languages.

Eligibility Criterion 2 (population)

I only included studies of reports about the potential health effects (negative or positive changes in health outcomes) of health interventions (any action intended to improve or maintain the health of an individual or group). The reports could be about the same condition or intervention, or they could be a mix. Reports had to be focused (i.e. primarily about) the effects of a health intervention, i.e. studies of reports about legal issues around an intervention, for example, were ineligible.

Eligibility Criterion 3 (study design)

For a study to be eligible, the researchers had to have used at least one explicit, *a priori*, generic criterion to measure the quality of reports. Generic meant not being tied to: a specific intervention (e.g. chemotherapy), or category of interventions (e.g. cancer treatments); a specific illness or injury (e.g. breast cancer), or category of conditions (e.g. cancer); or specific evidence (e.g. a systematic review of breast cancer treatments).

Studies were excluded if they only measured the quality of the underlying evidence (the subject of the report), or if they only measured the factual accuracy of reports. Semantically,

the term “quality” can be used to describe whether reports are about reliable evidence, or whether they are factually accurate. I excluded criteria that measure quality by these definitions to once more avoid “mixing apples and oranges”.

Eligibility Criterion 4 (reporting)

Finally, to be included, studies had to specify: the sampling frame (i.e. where the news reports were sampled from); the selection criteria for the reports; and the selection technique (i.e. how the reports were sampled). This means case studies of single reports were ineligible.

Pilot

I conducted a pilot with two additional reviewers to clarify the eligibility criteria. For the pilot, I selected five potentially eligible studies of which I was already aware (Appendix 1). That the studies were “potentially eligible” means I was aware of them before finalising the protocol, and I at least knew they were studies of health news reports, but I had not applied the eligibility criteria to them. For the pilot, I organized all such studies by the first authors’ last names, from A to Z, then by year, from present to past. I selected the first paper with a specified publication year, and every 10th paper after the first, to get a variation of samples and methods. The pilot contributed to clarification described in the discussion section.

Search strategy

I searched for eligible primary studies in the following five databases:

- PubMed (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed) on May 24, 2018,
- Google Scholar (www.scholar.google.com) on June 21 and 22,
- Open Grey (www.opengrey.eu), on June 22,
- Grey Literature Report (www.greylit.org), on June 22, and
- ProQuest Dissertations & Theses (Global Full text plus UK and Ireland abstracts) (www.proquest.com), on June 25.

I developed my PubMed search string (Box 4) using terms from the titles and abstracts of the potentially eligible studies of which I was aware before drafting the protocol. I extracted three groups of terms from those studies: 1) terms for news; 2) terms for media, including specific media; and 3) terms for quality or analysis. I included any Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) terms that fit in one of the groups, and added missing terms for media specified in the protocol (e.g. “podcast”). By using a string that would capture the potentially eligible studies of which I was aware before the search (of those in PubMed with abstracts), I would likely capture any similar study. I used the PubMed string as the basis for the strings used in other databases (Appendix 2).

The Google Scholar searches were intended to identify any eligible studies in journals that do not typically publish health or health-related research. However, I already considered it unlikely that there were any such studies, for the same reasons I considered it unlikely that I would find an existing review with a research objective similar to mine in such a journal (Appendix 1). Moreover, Google Scholar does not let you limit searches to titles and abstracts

(only to titles), making it difficult to retrieve results that are both comprehensive and manageable. Therefore, I conducted two searches limited to titles, and one search not limited to titles. A sample of 100 records out of 3020 were screened from the second search limited to titles, and a sample of 100 records out of 4,180,000 were screened from the search not limited to titles.

Amongst the results from all three Google Scholar searches, one study was included in this review (Stassen, 2016). The study was a thesis, i.e. not a study in a journal that does not typically publish health research. Hence, I did not consider it worthwhile to conduct further searches in Google Scholar, or conduct any searches in Scopus (www.scopus.com), which I had planned to do in the protocol.

In addition to searching databases, I checked an arbitrary sample of nine reference lists, from the first articles included after assessing the full texts for eligibility. All 42 studies I thought might be eligible before finalising the protocol were also screened.

Box 4: PubMed search string, May 24, 2018

```
(((news[Title/Abstract]) OR reporting[Title/Abstract])) AND (((((((((((media[Title/Abstract]) OR print[Title/Abstract]) OR newspaper*[Title/Abstract]) OR magazine*[Title/Abstract]) OR broadcast[Title/Abstract]) OR radio[Title/Abstract]) OR podcast*[Title/Abstract]) OR television[Title/Abstract]) OR news website*[Title/Abstract]) OR news site*[Title/Abstract]) OR mass media[MeSH Terms])) AND (((((quality[Title/Abstract]) OR accuracy[Title/Abstract]) OR content analysis[Title/Abstract]) OR inadequate[Title/Abstract]) OR incomplete[Title/Abstract])
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Study selection

Screening search results was done in two rounds. First, a second reviewer and I screened titles and abstracts. Second, we screened full texts of studies included from the first round. We discussed and resolved disagreements after each round. To register our judgements, we used the systematic review software Rayyan (www.rayyan.qcri.org) (Ouzzani, et al., 2016). Where the second reviewer and I could not reach a consensus, a third reviewer was brought in to arbitrate. The same process was applied to screen the potentially eligible studies of which I was aware before conducting the database searches. Screening reference lists included a third, initial round, where I alone screened titles.

Data extraction

I extracted: descriptive data about the population; stated objectives; sampling frames; selection criteria and techniques; reported subgroup analyses; the tools and individual criteria used to measure the quality of news reports; and descriptive data about the development of the tools. A second reviewer checked a sample of data from three studies. Only reported data were extracted. For example, when a study did not report the country or countries in which reports were published, I did not code the reports by country myself, or contact the study authors for that information.

Data about the population (i.e. the sample of news reports) included: 1) the total number of reports assessed; 2) the category or categories of media in which they were published; 3) the country or countries in which they were published; 4) the time period in which they were

published; 5) the category or categories of interventions reported on; and 6) the financial model or models of the news outlets.

All categories were predetermined. The categories of media were: newspapers; magazines; radio; podcasts; television; and news websites. The categories of intervention were: “modern” medicine (aka. “academic”, “conventional” or “Western” medicine); “alternative” medicine (aka. “complementary”, “traditional” or “natural” medicine); screening; surgery; devices; diet; exercise; lifestyle; and systems and policies. Financial model was categorized as either “commercial” or “non-commercial” (public or independent).

If the researchers used a specific tool to measure the quality of the reports, I extracted the title of the tool, e.g. Index of Scientific Quality. If the tool did not have a title, I named it after the first included study in which it was used, e.g. “Moynihan et al. 2000”. If the researchers specified a tool that they adapted, I noted this in brackets, e.g. “Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)”.

Data management

I entered all data, including page references, manually into a Microsoft Excel (2016) spreadsheet, with one sheet for descriptive data (sample size, categories of media, etc.), and one sheet for the criteria used to measure quality of news reports. The criteria were copied and pasted as rows in a second spreadsheet, for analysis. In the second spreadsheet, there was a column for each IHC Key Concept, represented by number. In other words the list of criteria were diagonally across from the list of IHC Key Concepts. The second reviewer and I used separate copies of this spreadsheet to conduct our independent analyses, then combined our

assessments in a single copy, to identify and resolve disagreements, as described in the subsection on the analysis. For organizational purposes, each criterion from each study was given a unique reference number, by combining the last name of the study's first author, and the year the study was published—e.g. andrew2016_001, andrew2016_002, etc.

Quality assessment

I assessed both the quality of each tool as a whole, and the quality of each individual criterion.

At the tool level, I checked whether there was a description of the tool's development, whether the tool was piloted, whether the researchers tested inter-rater agreement (reliability), and whether they conducted any other type of evaluation of the tool.

At the criterion level, another reviewer and I independently assessed whether each criterion—in addition to being explicit and *a priori*—was a clear and appropriate measure of quality, then resolved any differences between our assessments. Criteria were inappropriate if they: 1) were not generic; 2) measured factual accuracy; or 3) were not sensible.

Global scores were also excluded. Global scores are difficult to interpret because they do not tell you which parts of a news report are problematic. Moreover, they are difficult to compare across studies using different scoring systems. Criteria that were composites of other criteria in the same tool were considered a type of global score.

Analysis

Criteria used to measure the quality of reports were mapped against the IHC Key Concepts. The IHC Key Concept was uniquely useful for this review because, as stated in the background section: it is intended to be relevant to the general public (i.e. general news audiences); and it is a framework that can be used to evaluate measurement tools. A second reviewer and I independently judged which IHC Key Concepts related to each criterion. We then discussed and resolved any disagreements. Finally, I grouped the criteria, informed by the IHC Key Concepts to which each criterion was considered related. A second reviewer assessed whether the groupings were sensible.

We included criteria related to the costs of health interventions, in addition to criteria related to effects. Cost is an important consideration when making decisions about health interventions, which is reflected in the explanation of IHC Key Concept 3.6: “Decisions about whether or not to use a treatment should be informed by the balance between the potential benefits and the potential harms, costs and other advantages and disadvantages” (Austvoll-Dahlgren, et al., 2017, p. 11).

Ethical considerations

This study did not include notable ethical considerations.

Results

Twenty-nine primary studies were identified for inclusion in this review (Figure 1). Of the 29, 13 (45%) were amongst the potentially eligible studies of which I was aware before finalising the protocol (Appendix 1). Two of the studies are theses, while the rest were published in scientific journals. Two are in Norwegian (Høye & Hjortdahl, 2002; Johansen, et al., 1996), the rest in English.

Figure 1: Flow diagram of study selection process

Records and full texts were excluded if they did not meet one of the four eligibility criteria. The criteria were applied in order, and if a study failed to satisfy one, we did not apply the others. In Box 5, I give an example of a study that was excluded after assessing the full text for each eligibility criterion, respectively.

Studies were excluded if they only described the content of reports, as opposed to measuring the quality of reports. In some cases, such studies included one or more descriptive variables similar to criteria in studies included in this review. For example, a study by Caulfield et al. was excluded for only describing news reports about vitamin D supplementation (Box 5), but the results included whether potential harms of the intervention were mentioned—the same results you would get from applying some of the criteria included in this review.

Including such studies would likely have required substantially more work, without necessarily contributing substantially to the results. I would have to develop a more complex search strategy, screen a larger number of records and full texts, and assess whether each descriptive variable could be framed as a measure of quality, as I have defined it.

Box 5: Examples of full-text articles excluded

Eligibility Criterion 1: The sample includes reports labelled by the researchers as news, published in newspapers or magazines, on television, radio or podcasts, or on news websites.
Molnar et al. studied advice columns, not news reports (1999).

Eligibility Criterion 2: The sample includes reports about the effects of health interventions.
Partridge et al. studied news reports about “non-medical” use of drugs, i.e. non-health interventions (Partridge, et al., 2011).

Eligibility Criterion 3: At least one explicit, *a priori*, generic criterion was used to measure the quality of the reports.

Chau et al. compare the content of news coverage of sit-stand desks to specific recommendations, i.e. do not use generic criteria (2018). Caulfield et al. set out to “examine the nature of media coverage” of Vitamin D supplements, i.e. describe news reports, not measure their quality (2014). And Cooper et al. “evaluate the evidence base for dietary health claims reported in UK newspapers”, i.e. evaluate the quality of the underlying evidence, not the quality of the reports (2012, p. 665).

Eligibility Criterion 4: The sampling frame, and the selection criteria and technique are specified.

Molitor specifies a sampling frame—five particular newspapers—but does not explicitly specify any criteria or technique for selecting reports from the frame for the study (1993).

Study characteristics

Population

Table 1 is a list of all studies included in the review and characteristics of the respective samples of news reports, i.e. the populations. I have not done any categorisation myself. The data on media, countries, time periods, and intervention categories reported in this review reflect the authors' categorisations. The financial model of included news outlets—whether they were commercial or non-commercial (public or independent) was not specified in any study.

Table 1: Included studies

Study	Sample size*	Medium/Media[†]	Country/Countries	Time period(s)[‡]	Intervention category/categories[§]
Andrew et al. (2016)	107	Newspapers, TV	Canada, US	2011-2014	Not explicitly specified
Basu and Hogard (2008)	29	Newspapers	UK	2015	Diet
Bonevski et al. (2008)	222	News websites, newspapers, TV	Australia	2004-2007	“Alternative” medicine
Bubela et al. (2008)	553	Newspapers	Australia, Canada, New Zealand, UK, US	1995-2005	“Alternative” medicine, “modern” medicine
Cassels et al. (2003)	356	Newspapers	Canada	2000	“Modern” medicine
Hackman and Moe (1999)	148	Newspapers	Not explicitly specified	1995	Diet
Haneef et al. (2015)	130	News websites	Canada, UK, US	2013-2014	“Modern” medicine, other
Heaner (2009)	161	Newspapers	US	2008	Diet, exercise
Høye and Hjortdahl (2002)	492	Newspapers	Norway	1998-2000	“Modern” medicine
Iaboli et al. (2010)	146	Magazines, newspapers	Italy	2008	“Modern” medicine, other
Johansen et al. (1996)	30	Newspapers	Norway	1995	“Modern” medicine, other
Kininmonth et al. (2017)	141	Newspapers	UK	2014	Diet
Krauth and Apollonio (2015)	26	Magazines, newspapers	US	2004-2012	Lifestyle
Lewis et al. (2010)	17	Newspapers	Australia	2007	“Alternative” medicine
Motl et al. (2005)	60	Magazines, news websites, newspapers	US	2002	Not explicitly specified
Moynihan et al. (2000)	207	Newspapers, TV	US	1994-1998	“Modern” medicine

Study	Sample size*	Medium/Media†	Country/Countries	Time period(s) ‡	Intervention category/categories§
Nichols and Chase (2005)	321	Newspapers	Trinidad and Tobago	2003	Not explicitly specified
Rabi et al. (2009)	89	Magazines, newspapers	Not explicitly specified	2007	“Modern” medicine
Robinson et al. (2013)	160	Newspapers	UK	2010-2011	“Modern” medicine
Robinson et al. (2018)	126	News websites	New Zealand	2014	“Modern” medicine, surgery
Schwitzer (2008)	500	Magazines, newspapers, TV	US	2006-2008	Devices, diet, “modern” medicine, screening, surgery
Smith et al. (2005)	104	Unclear	Australia	2004	“Modern” medicine, screening, other
Stassen (2016)	489	Newspapers	South Africa	2014	Not explicitly specified
Sumner et al. (2014)	668	Print and news websites	UK	2011	Not explicitly specified
Sumner et al. (2016)	582	Not explicitly specified	UK	2011	Not explicitly specified
Walsh-Childers et al. (2016)	1889	Magazines, news websites, newspapers, TV	Not explicitly specified	2005-2013	Diet, “modern” medicine, screening, other
Wilson et al. (2009)	1230	News websites, newspapers, TV	Australia	2004-2008	“Alternative” medicine, diet, exercise, “modern” medicine, screening, surgery
Woloshin and Schwartz (2006)	187	Newspapers, radio, TV	Canada, US	2002-2003	Not explicitly specified
Yavchitz et al. (2012)	41	Not explicitly specified	Not explicitly specified	2009-2010	Devices, “modern” medicine, surgery, other

*Number of reports included in study, not necessarily number of reports about effects of health interventions

†As per categories pre-specified in the protocol (newspapers, magazines, TV, radio, podcasts, and news websites)

‡Time period of when reports were published or studied

§As per categories pre-specified in the protocol (“modern” medicine, “alternative” medicine, screening, surgery, devices, diet, exercise, lifestyle, and systems and policies)

Population: Sample sizes

Sample sizes ranged between 17 and 1889 reports. The average sample was 318 reports, while the median was 160. The total sample for all studies combined is 9211 news reports. The sample size is the number of news reports included in a study, not necessarily the number of reports about the effects of health interventions—i.e. the samples reported here may include reports about exposures, for example. This issue will be addressed before conducting the planned meta-analysis, separately from this dissertation.

Population: Media

Pre-specified media were: newspapers, magazines, TV, radio, podcasts, and news websites. Table 2 lists the number of studies per medium. Reports are not represented in the table if: the authors did not explicitly specify the media (Yavchitz, et al., 2012; Sumner, et al., 2016); the authors did not explicitly specify whether “print” refers to either newspapers or magazines, or both (Sumner, et al., 2014) or the authors’ categorization is unclear (Smith, et al., 2005).

The studies by Sumner et al. (2016) and Yavchitz et al. (2012) were included despite the media not being explicitly specified, because the researchers’ samples came from databases of reports published in pre-specified media. The categorization by Smith et al. is unclear because the authors write on page 190 that they “concentrated on five websites,” but in Box 2, on page 192 refer to both “Print” and “Online”. Note that Andrew et al. also included non-news media.

The number of studies that measured the quality of reports published in print versus online should be interpreted with some caution. For example, in the largest study, Walsh-Childers et al. write that news reports “must have been published on the news organization’s website,” (p. 3), but then categorize reports published on newspapers’ websites as newspaper reports. That said, newspapers as combined print and online outlets have clearly been the most popular source of reports.

Table 2: Studies per medium

Medium	Studies
Newspapers	24
TV	7
Magazines	6
News websites	6
Radio	1
Podcasts	0

Population: Countries

Most studies were of reports published in high-income and English-speaking countries, as shown in Table 3. In four studies, the country or countries of reports are not explicitly specified, hence the reports in those studies are not represented in the table.

Table 3: Studies per country

Country	Studies
US	9
UK	7
Australia	5
Canada	5
New Zealand	2
Norway	2
Italy	1
South Africa	1
Trinidad and Tobago	1

Population: Time Periods

Most of the studies measured the quality of news reports published after 2000 (Table 4). In some cases, the time period reported in the study may not be the exact time period in which the reports were published. For example, in the study by Walsh-Childers et al. (2016), the time period reported is when the quality of the reports was measured. However, none of the included studies were intended to be historical analyses, so any difference between the period in which reports were published and the period in which they were assessed should be minor. Seven studies reported time periods within the last five years (2013 to 2018) (Table 1). The earliest reported year was 1994 (Moynihan, et al., 2000).

Table 4: Studies per time period

Time period	Studies
1990-1999	5
2000-2009	17
2010-2018	12

Population: Intervention categories

My pre-specified intervention categories were: “modern” medicine; “alternative” medicine; screening; surgery; devices; diet; exercise; lifestyle; and systems and policies. Table 5 shows the distribution of studies amongst these categories. The most common category was “modern” medicine, followed by diet. I have categorized reports about diagnostic tests as reports about screening interventions, given that they are described by the authors as reports about interventions, and the same criteria are applied to those reports and reports about medicines, etc. None of the studies included reports about health system or policy interventions.

Seven studies are excluded from Table 1 because the authors did not categorize the interventions that the news reports were about. Another seven included some reports that could be placed in one of my pre-specified categories, and some that could not. In Table 1, the latter reports are given the intervention category “Other”. For example, Haneef et al. included reports about “pharmacological” interventions, which I have categorized as being about “modern” medicine, but also “non-pharmacological” interventions, which could fall under “Alternative” medicine, devices, diet, etc. (2015, p. 3), so I have categorized the non-pharmacological reports as “Other”.

Table 5: Studies per intervention category

Intervention category	Studies
“Modern” medicine	15
Diet	7
“Alternative” medicine	4
Screening	4
Surgery	4
Devices	2
Exercise	2
Lifestyle	1
Systems and policies	0

Objectives, sampling frames, and selection criteria and techniques

The stated objectives, sampling frames, and selection criteria and techniques are listed in Appendix 3. Eight studies do not explicitly state an objective or aim. Researchers used a variety of sampling frames, and selection criteria and techniques, and provided varying degrees of detail. For example, in terms of sampling frame, some studies named specific outlets (specific newspapers, magazines etc.), while others only named a database, or a category of media (e.g. newspapers, magazines, etc.).

Reported subgroup analyses

Appendix 4 is an overview of the reported subgroup analyses. Note that these are only analyses comparing subgroups of reports—not, for example, comparing results for individual criteria. Twenty-two studies reported at least one subgroup analysis of reports. The most frequent factors used for subgroup analyses were the outlet (i.e. the specific newspaper, magazine, etc.), category of intervention, and medium.

Tools

In the 29 studies included in this review, researchers used 20 tools to measure the quality of news reports. Table 6 shows the number of studies per tool, while Table 7 shows the tool used in each study. Studies using the Health News Review tool (n = 3) are counted with studies using the earlier-developed Media Doctor Australia tool, since they are ostensibly the same tool given a different name (Schwitzer, 2008, p. 0701). However, they are not exactly the same, as explained later in the results. The tool developed by Moynihan et al. was a starting point for several other tools, including the Media Doctor Australia tool (Smith, et al., 2005, p. 191). Still, there has clearly not been a standard tool. None of the included studies used the Quality Index for health-related Media Reports (QIMR).

Table 6: Studies per tool

Tool	Studies*
Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	7 (3)
Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	3
Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	2
Sumner et al. 2014 (original)	2
Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	1
Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	1
Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	1
Hackman and Moe 1999 (original)	1
Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	1
Heaner 2009 (original)	1
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)	1
Iaboli et al. 2010 (original)	1
Motl et al. 2005 (original)	1
Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)	1
Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	1
Rabi et al. 2009 (adapted from Cassels et al. 2008)	1
Robinson et al. 2018 (original)	1
Tabloid Analysis Tool	1
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	1
Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)	1

*Robinson et al. (2018) use two tools, so the study is counted twice

Table 7: Tools by study

Study	Tool
Andrew et al. (2016)	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)
Basu and Hogard (2008)	Tabloid Analysis Tool
Bonevski et al. (2008)	Media Doctor Australia
Bubela et al. (2008)	Bubela et al. 2008 (original)
Cassels et al. (2003)	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)
Hackman and Moe (1999)	Hackman and Moe 1999 (original)
Haneef et al. (2015)	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)
Heaner (2009)	Heaner 2009 (original)
Høye and Hjortdahl (2002)	Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)
Iaboli et al. (2010)	Iaboli et al. 2010 (original)
Johansen et al. (1996)	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)
Kininmonth et al. (2017)	Robinson et al. 2013
Krauth and Apollonio (2015)	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)
Lewis et al. (2010)	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)
Motl et al. (2005)	Motl et al. 2005 (original)
Moynihan et al. (2000)	Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)
Nichols and Chase (2005)	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)
Rabi et al. (2009)	Rabi et al. 2009 (adapted from Cassels et al. 2008)
Robinson et al. (2013)	Robinson et al. 2013 (original)
Robinson et al. (2018)	Robinson et al. 2018 (original) and Media Doctor Australia
Schwitzer (2008)	Health News Review (Media Doctor Australia)
Smith et al. (2005)	Media Doctor Australia
Stassen (2016)	Health News Review (Media Doctor Australia)
Sumner et al. (2014)	Sumner et al. 2014 (original)
Sumner et al. (2016)	Sumner et al. 2014
Walsh-Childers et al. (2016)	Health News Review (Media Doctor Australia)
Wilson et al. (2009)	Media Doctor Australia
Woloshin and Schwartz (2006)	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)
Yavchitz et al. (2012)	Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)

Quality assessment

Quality assessment: Tools

To assess each tool as a whole, I looked at whether the researchers piloted the tool, whether they tested inter-rater agreement (reliability), and whether they conducted any other type of evaluation (Appendix 5). If any of the three were not reported, I assumed it was not done.

For five of the 20 tools, there was no description of the development, or reference to a description. Where a description was provided or referenced, the amount of information varied from the entire paper describing the development of the ISQ (Oxman, et al., 1993), to a single sentence, for example: “A coding instrument was developed and pilot-tested” (Cassels, et al., 2003, p. 1137).

About half of the tools (n = 11, 55%) were piloted. Inter-rater agreement was tested for a minority of tools (7%). Any other type of evaluation was conducted for three (15%) of the tools. Oxman et al. tested the sensibility of the ISQ (1993, p. 991), while Heaner tested the content validity of their tool (2009, p. 95). Basu and Hogard state they tested the “validity” of the tool, but do not describe what this entailed (2008, p. 1126).

Quality assessment: Individual criteria

After I had extracted all criteria from the 29 included studies, a second reviewer and I independently assessed each individual criterion, then compared our assessments and resolved any differences. We ended up including 200 criteria and excluding 168. We did not attempt to

remove duplicates (or isolate unique criteria), where—ostensibly—the same tool was used in several studies. This was in case of any modification to the tool between studies. Indeed, I identified such modifications.

For example, in the earliest included study in which the Health News Review tool is used, Schwitzer writes: “The rating instrument used (http://www.healthnewsreview.org/ratings_info.php) includes ten criteria used by the Australian and Canadian Media Doctor sites” (2008, p. 0701). Since there are only 10 criteria in the Health News Review tool, it should be same as the Media Doctor Australia tool. However, in three studies, one of the Media Doctor Australia criteria asks whether there was (“objective”) “evidence” supporting the “treatment” or “intervention” (Smith, et al., 2005, p. 191; Robinson, et al., 2018, p. 927; Wilson, et al., 2009). Whereas the corresponding Health News Review criterion asks whether the “quality” of the evidence has been “discussed” or “grasped”, (Schwitzer, 2008, p. 0702; Stassen, 2016, p. 51; Walsh-Childers, et al., 2016) which is a different question.

Moreover, Bonevski et al. use the Media Doctor Australia tool, but the criterion there asks whether the “type of” evidence supporting the treatment is reported (p. 2), which is more specific than asking whether there is (objective) evidence. Had we only included the first version of the Media Doctor Australia criterion, and considered the corresponding criteria in other studies as duplicates, I would have missed differences such as these.

Of the 168 excluded criteria, we excluded 26 for being insufficiently clear. For example, the tool developed by Robinson et al. includes the criterion: “Does the article compare statistics, are they misused or misrepresented?” (2013). There is no further explanation, so it is unclear

what type of statistics the criterion refers to, and what is meant by “misused” or “misrepresented”.

We excluded 11 global scores and composite criteria. For example, Haneef et al. measured different types of “spin”, including the failure to report on adverse events, or favouring “statistically significant” outcomes (2015). We included criteria measuring different types of spin, but excluded the criteria that were composites of different spin.

Most criteria (n = 131) were excluded for being inappropriate. Criteria could be inappropriate in three different ways. First, they could be non-generic. For example, criteria used by Rabi et al. (2009) were excluded for being tied to a specific outcome (cardiovascular events), a specific systematic review and meta-analysis (Nissen & Wolski, 2007), and a specific medication (Rosiglitazone).

Second, criteria were deemed inappropriate if they measured whether something was factually accurate. For example, several criteria used by Heaner (2009) were excluded for measuring whether information such as the sample size and population were reported “accurately”. Note that we included studies that used the term “accuracy”, as long as they met the eligibility criteria for the review—e.g. the study by Krauth & Apollonio.

Finally, criteria were inappropriate if they were not sensible. For example, Hackman and Moe used the criterion: “News based on a peer-reviewed study” (Hackman & Moe, 1999, p. 1565). This is not a sensible criterion because peer-reviewed research can be unreliable (Jefferson, et al., 2002). Another example is criteria that appear to conflate “statistical significance” and importance, for example a criterion in the tool developed by Robinson and colleagues: “Does

the article state whether the findings are statistically significant?” (2013). Findings can be false, even if they are “statistically significant” (Ioannidis, 2005), and the term “statistical significance” is problematic (Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care, 2017).

Mapping of criteria

In addition to including and excluding individual criteria, the second reviewer and I independently mapped the included criteria against the IHC Key Concepts. Table 8 shows how often (or rarely) each IHC Key Concept was found relevant to a criterion. Note that two “new” IHC Key Concepts were used in the mapping—two concepts that are in the latest draft version of the list (Oxman, et al., [unpublished]), but not in the latest published list—as mentioned in the background section. The two are: verbal descriptions of treatment effects can be misleading; and, the problem and the treatment options being considered may not be the right ones. I included the two because they were particularly relevant to so many criteria, and missing from the latest published list. Note also that 21 included criteria are excluded from Table 8, because it was unclear to which IHC Key Concepts those criteria specifically relate.

Table 8: Criteria per related IHC Key Concept

Concept	Criteria*
3.6 Do the advantages outweigh the disadvantages?	39
3.2 Are you very different from the people studied?	25
New 2.3a Verbal descriptions of treatment effects can be misleading	18
1.1 Treatments can harm	17
3.3 Are the treatments practical in your setting?	14
2.15 Fair comparisons with few people or outcome events can be misleading	13
1.7 Beware of conflicting interests	12
2.13 Relative measures of effects can be misleading	10
3.1 Do the outcomes measured matter to you?	9
New 3.1a The problem and the treatment options being considered may not be the right ones	9
1.3 Association is not the same as causation	7
1.9 Earlier is not necessarily better	7
2.2 Comparison groups should be similar	7
2.1 Comparisons are needed to identify treatment effects	5
2.8 Consider all the relevant fair comparisons	5
1.6 Expert opinion is not always right	4
2.16 Confidence intervals should be reported	3
2.11 All fair comparisons and outcomes should be reported	2
2.9 Reviews of fair comparisons should be systematic	2
3.4 Do treatment comparisons reflect your circumstances?	2
3.5 How certain is the evidence?	2
2.12 Subgroup analyses may be misleading	1
2.17 Don't confuse "statistical significance" with "importance"	1
2.18 Don't confuse "no evidence of a difference" with "evidence of no difference"	1
2.4 Comparison groups should be treated equally	1
2.5 People should not know which treatment they get	1
2.6 Peoples' outcomes should be assessed similarly 2.7	1
2.7 All should be followed up	1
1.2 Anecdotes are unreliable evidence	0
1.4 Common practice is not always evidence-based	0
1.5 Newer is not necessarily better	0
1.8 More is not necessarily better	0
1.10 Hope may lead to unrealistic expectations	0
1.11 Explanations about how treatments work can be wrong	0
1.12 Dramatic treatment effects are rare	0
2.14 Average measures of effects can be misleading	0
2.3 Peoples' outcomes should be analyzed in their original groups	0
2.10 Peer-review and publication does not guarantee reliable information	0

*Excludes 21 criteria considered probably or potentially, but not clearly, related to particular IHC Key Concepts

Thirty-nine criteria were considered clearly related to IHC Key Concept 3.6—Do the advantages outweigh the disadvantages? Between 10 and 25 were considered clearly related to one of seven IHC Key Concepts. Between two and nine were considered clearly related to one of 13 concepts. A single criterion was considered related to one of seven concepts. And none of the 200 criteria were considered related to 10 of the concepts. Twenty-one criteria related to reporting on study design and risk of bias were seen as probably or potentially related to 15 of the IHC Key Concepts. These are listed later, in the description of the group where these criteria were placed.

None of the included criteria were considered even potentially related to the following eight IHC Key Concepts:

- Common practice is not always evidence-based (1.4),
- newer is not necessarily better (1.5),
- more is not necessarily better (1.8),
- hope may lead to unrealistic expectations (1.10),
- explanations about how treatments work can be wrong (1.11),
- dramatic treatment effects are rare (1.12),
- peer review and publication does not guarantee reliable information (2.10), or
- average measures of effects can be misleading (2.14).

In fact, some criteria appear inconsistent with IHC Key Concepts 1.5 and 2.10. These criteria ask whether the treatment discussed in the news report is “genuinely new”—see for example the criterion used by Smith et al. (2005, p. 191), and whether the research discussed was peer-reviewed—e.g. the criterion used by Hackman & Moe (1999, p. 1565).

Grouping of criteria

Informed by the results of mapping the criteria against the IHC Key Concepts, I divided the 200 included criteria into 19 groups (

Table 9). Three criteria appear in two groups, because the criterion or the response options are relatively broad, relating them to more IHC Key Concepts. All included criteria are listed in Appendix 6. Summaries of each group follow this subsection.

The two largest groups are Groups R (n = 41) and S (n = 39)— criteria related to extrapolations from one (human) population, intervention or outcome to another, and criteria related to reporting on the advantages and disadvantages of health interventions. Four groups include between 12 and 21 criteria, nine groups include between 2 and 9 criteria, and the last four groups include a single criterion each.

Table 9: Criteria groups in order of related IHC Key Concepts

Group	Criteria*
Group A: Criteria related to reporting on associations and randomization	7
Group B: Criteria related to reporting on opinions	4
Group C: Criteria related to reporting on conflicts of interest	12
Group D: Criteria related to "disease mongering"	7
Group E: Criteria related to reporting on the need for comparisons	5
Group F: Criteria related to reporting on blinding	1
Group G: Criteria related to reporting on loss to follow-up	1
Group H: Criteria related to reporting on study design and risk of bias in general	21
Group I: Criteria related to reporting on consistency between studies	5
Group J: Criteria related to reporting on the play of chance	13
Group K: Criteria related to qualitative descriptions of effects	19
Group L: Criteria related to selective reporting in news reports	2
Group M: Criteria related to reporting on subgroup analyses	1
Group N: Criteria related to reporting absolute risk	9
Group O: Criteria related to reporting on a lack of evidence	1
Group P: Criteria related to reporting on options	9
Group Q: Criteria related to reporting on animal studies	6
Group R: Criteria related to extrapolations from one (human) population, intervention or outcome to another	41
Groups S: Criteria related to reporting on advantages and disadvantages	39

**Three criteria appear in two groups*

Group A: Criteria related to reporting on associations and randomization

Group A includes seven criteria from seven studies and six tools. Three of the criteria focus on randomization, three focus on conflating correlation and causation, and one focuses on “within-group (or over-all [sic] within)” comparisons. One of the criteria is descriptive, measuring whether randomization is specified or not. The other six require some judgement about what is being claimed, what cautions are provided, or what is the focus of the report.

Group B: Criteria related to reporting on opinions

Group B includes four criteria from four studies and two tools. Three criteria are the same, from the ISQ, and the fourth is from the Tabloid Analysis Tool (TAT). The ISQ criterion asks

whether opinions in general are distinguished from “facts”, while the TAT criterion asks whether statements attributed to experts, researchers or studies specifically are substantiated.

Group C: Criteria related to reporting on conflicts of interest

Group C includes 12 criteria from 11 studies and 9 tools. Some of the criteria ask whether the funding source of the research is reported, whereas others look at whether conflicts of interests are reported. The Media Doctor Australia (or Health News Review) criterion asks whether “independent sources” are “used” or “sought”. If this in and of itself was the criterion, it would be excluded as inappropriate, since sources may provide unreliable information even if they are independent.

Group D: Criteria related to “disease mongering”

Seven criteria in seven studies measured the presence of “disease mongering”. These were all from the Media Doctor Australia (or Health News Review) tool. Disease mongering is not defined in the earliest of the seven studies (Smith, et al., 2005), but there is a reference to an editorial on “selling sickness”, in which the term is defined as: “extending the boundaries of treatable illness to expand markets for new product” (Moynihan, et al., 2002, p. 886)

Group E: Criteria related to reporting on the need for comparisons

Group E includes five criteria from five studies and three tools. One asks whether there are claims about the benefits of an intervention “despite lack of comparator”, and another asks whether relevant cautions are provided about uncontrolled studies. The remaining three are

from the Media Doctor Australia tool and ask whether there is (“objective”) evidence “supporting” the intervention.

Group F: Criteria related to reporting on blinding

Group F includes a single criterion, from Bubela et al. 2008. The criterion asks whether “double-blinding” is specified in the news report. It is unclear who needs to be blinded for a study to be “double-blind”—i.e. what combination of participants, carers and researcher—reflecting a problem with definitions of blinding in medicine (Devereaux, et al., 2001).

Group G: Criteria related to reporting on loss to follow-up

Group G includes a single, descriptive criterion from a single study. The criterion asks whether withdrawals or dropouts are specified.

Group H: Criteria related to reporting on study design and risk of bias in general

Group H includes 21 criteria, from 15 studies and 10 tools. From the descriptions provided, it is somewhat unclear to which IHC Key Concepts the 21 criteria specifically relate. For example, criteria asking whether “study design” is reported, may or may not refer to animal studies, and criteria asking whether “limitations” are reported may only refer to specific methods (e.g. blinding), and not overarching designs (e.g. observational studies). The criteria in Group H were considered potentially or probably relevant to:

- anecdotes are unreliable evidence (1.2) (in this context referring to case studies),

- association is not the same as causation (1.3) (in this context referring to observational study designs),
- comparisons are needed to identify treatment effects (2.1),
- comparison groups should be similar (2.2),
- people's outcomes should be analysed in their original groups (2.3),
- comparison groups should be treated equally (2.4),
- people should not know which treatment they get (2.5),
- peoples' outcomes should be assessed similarly (2.6),
- all should be followed up (2.7),
- consider all the relevant fair comparisons (2.8),
- reviews of fair comparisons should be systematic (2.9),
- “Do the outcomes measured matter to you?” (3.1),
- “Are you very different from the people studied?” (3.2),
- “Are the treatments practical in your setting?” (3.3), and
- “Do treatment comparisons reflect your circumstances? (3.4).

Group I: Criteria related to reporting on consistency between studies

Group I includes five criteria from five studies and three tools. Two criteria are the same criterion from the ISQ, which asks whether “consistency of evidence (between studies)” is considered and whether the assessment is “well-founded (not misleading)”. Another two criteria ask whether the study “differs from previous research”. The fifth criterion asks whether “efforts” are made to “interpret the results in the context of current evidence.”

Group J: Criteria related to reporting on the play of chance

Group J includes 13 criteria from 12 studies and nine tools. Some are descriptive, asking whether the sample size is reported. The ISQ criterion here asks whether there is a “well-founded (not misleading) assessment of the precision of any estimates that are reported or of the probability that any of the reported findings might be due to chance,” while the criterion used by Woloshin and Schwartz asks whether relevant cautions are provided about small studies, which they define as studies with less than 30 subjects (2006, p. 578).

Group K: Criteria related to qualitative descriptions of effects

Group K includes 18 criteria, from 14 studies and eight tools. Four ask whether sensationalist language is used. The other four ask whether effects in general, harms specifically, or benefits specifically are quantified. Three of the criteria in this group are also included in other groups: two in Group N (criteria related to reporting absolute risk), and one in Group S (criteria related to reporting on advantages and disadvantages).

Group L: Criteria related to selective reporting in news reports

Group L includes two criteria from two studies and two tools. One asks whether “statistically significant” outcomes are selectively reported. The other asks whether positive secondary outcomes are selectively reported.

Group M: Criteria related to reporting on subgroup analyses

Group M includes a single criterion. The criterion asks whether there is focus on an “inappropriate” subgroup. It is somewhat unclear what is meant by “inappropriate”.

Group N: Criteria related to reporting absolute risk

Group N includes nine criteria from eight studies and seven tools. Five focus on benefits, three refer to any “risk”, and one focuses on harms. Six of the criteria refer to both relative and absolute risks. Two of the criteria in this group also appear in Group K (criteria related to qualitative descriptions of effects).

In some studies, the Media Doctor Australia criterion refers to relative and absolute risks specifically, while in other studies it does not. This is another example of differences between corresponding criteria in studies that ostensibly use the same tool. Only criteria that explicitly refer to absolute risks are included in this group.

Group O: Criteria related to reporting on a lack of evidence

Group O includes a single criterion. The criterion here asks whether there is a claim of “equivalence” between interventions based on the lack of a “statistically significant” difference.

Group P: Criteria related to reporting on options

Group P includes nine criteria from eight studies and two tools. The criterion used by Cassels et al. distinguishes drug and non-drug alternative interventions (2003, p. 1136).

Group Q: Criteria related to reporting on animal studies

Group Q includes six criteria from six studies and four tools. All but one ask whether animal studies are used to make inferences about the effects of the intervention on humans. The last criterion asks whether relevant cautions are provided when reporting on animal studies.

Group R: Criteria related to extrapolations from one (human) population, intervention or outcome to another

Group R, the largest group, includes 41 criteria from 21 studies and 14 tools. Eighteen criteria relate to extrapolations from one (human) population to another, 11 to extrapolations from one intervention to another, and eight to extrapolations from one outcome to another. Three relate to extrapolations from one context to another, while one does not specify the type or types of extrapolation.

Group S: Criteria related to reporting on advantages and disadvantages

Group S, the final group, includes 39 criteria from 21 studies and 13 tools. The criteria relate to acknowledging potential harms (n = 17), potential benefits (n = 3), costs (n = 13), or any of the above (n = 6). The criteria vary from the descriptive—asking whether harms, benefits or

costs are mentioned or quantified—to ones that require more judgement, asking whether advantages and disadvantages are “adequately” discussed. One of the criteria in Group S also appears in Group K (criteria related to qualitative descriptions of effects).

Discussion

Twenty-nine studies were included in this review. Researchers most frequently studied news reports in newspapers, in English-speaking and high-income countries, over the last 20 years, about “modern” medicine or diet (not necessarily reports with all four characteristics). None of the included studies measured the quality of reports about health systems and policies, and no studies specified whether the outlets that published reports included in the study were commercial or non-commercial.

Twenty different tools were used to measure the quality of reports. Two-hundred criteria from those tools (54%) were included in the review, and 168 (46%) criteria were excluded. Some criteria were descriptive, requiring little judgement, for example whether the design of the study was mentioned in reports about health research. Others required more judgement, for example the ISQ criterion: “Is the assessment of the credibility (validity) of the evidence clear and well-founded (not misleading)?”

There was often little explanation of how judgements were made—for example “Study limitations [Not reported/Reported]” (Andrew, et al., 2016). Such criteria may have been interpreted and applied differently by different researchers in the same study. Moreover, criteria from different studies that seem similar, for example criteria that ask about “study

design” or “evidence quality”, may have been interpreted and applied differently across studies.

A second reviewer and I mapped the 200 criteria against the IHC Key Concepts. There were 21 criteria related to reporting on study design and risk of bias that were not clearly related to particular IHC Key Concepts, but potentially related to 15 of the concepts. None of the 200 criteria were clearly related to ten of the IHC Key Concepts. Some criteria appeared inconsistent with IHC Key Concepts.

I divided the 200 included criteria into 19 groups, informed by mapping them against the IHC Key Concepts. The two largest groups were Groups R (n = 41 criteria) and S (n = 39 criteria): criteria related to extrapolations from one (human) population, intervention or outcome to another; and criteria related to reporting on the advantages and disadvantages of health interventions.

Deviations from the protocol

Eligibility

I dropped the Condition, Context and Population (CoCoPop) framework suggested by Munn et al. for questions about prevalence (2015, pp. 148-149). In the study selection process, I found it was a poor fit for my question, mainly because it is unintuitive to think of news reports as having a condition. Furthermore, the “context” was obsolete since the only eligibility criterion in terms of context—that reports be published in one of the mediums specified in the protocol—was captured by my definition of the population. Therefore, I

instead considered eligibility in terms of population, study design, and reporting of study details.

I made it explicit that the criteria used to measure quality had to be *a priori* and generic, and that they had to be used to measure the quality of news reports, not describe their content, or measure the quality of the underlying evidence (see Box 5 at the beginning of the results section).

I did not exclude eligible studies if the reporting was inadequate for including results in the planned meta-analysis (Appendix 1)—e.g. studies that, in the results, do not differentiate between reports about interventions and exposures, such as the study by Kininmonth and colleagues. Instead, I included such studies, extracted the relevant data, and noted issues with the reporting, given that the studies were still useful for achieving the objective of this review.

I had planned to include studies regardless of language, but to save time, I only included studies in English or Norwegian—the two languages I speak fluently. Three studies in other languages appeared potentially eligible, based on the English abstracts, and were set aside for translation ahead of the planned meta-analysis. These studies included reports published in Austria (Kerschner, et al., 2015), Germany (Niewald, et al., 2018), and Catalonia (Solans-Domènech, et al., 2017), respectively

Search strategy and data extraction

I did not search the Scopus database (www.scopus.com). I had planned to search Scopus to identify studies in journals that do not generally publish health research. However, after

finding no such studies in test searches of Google Scholar, I decided searching Scopus was not worthwhile. To save time, I only screened an arbitrary sample of nine reference lists, as opposed to every reference list of every included study. Moreover, I did not conduct any citation searches. Also to save time, I alone extracted data, a sample of which was checked by a second reviewer, as opposed to dual, independent extraction.

Quality assessment

In the protocol, I describe plans to assess the risk of selection and detection bias (Appendix 1). Because that assessment relates to the planned meta-analysis, and would not be helpful for interpreting the results of this review, I have not included those assessments in my dissertation. I did assess the quality of the measurement tools and the quality of individual criteria. I excluded individual criteria if they were unclear, global scores (including composites), or inappropriate. Criteria were inappropriate if they were non-generic, measured factual accuracy, or were not sensible measures of quality. A second reviewer conducted this assessment independently. The reasons for excluding criteria were not specified in the protocol.

Reporting

I have not created the table of excluded studies that was going to contain:

1. studies with inadequate reporting for inclusion in the planned meta-analysis (including studies that only provide a global score),
2. studies of the quality of other health information in news reports, besides information about the effects of health interventions,

3. case studies of single reports, and
4. studies I was unable to translate.

The first and last categories are discussed in the subsection on deviations from the protocol in terms of eligibility. The second category did not make sense, because my definition of quality is specific to information about the effects of health interventions. I did not identify any case studies of single reports.

Strengths and limitations

Strengths

Focusing on the first objective in the protocol. It allowed me to spend more, necessary time and effort making sense of the criteria used in the included studies, and more, necessary space to describe how that objective was achieved, and to present the findings. At the same time, the protocol including plans for a meta-analysis meant that the objective and methods used in this review were selected specifically to make the planned meta-analysis straightforward and meaningful. The analysis presented here revealed important problems with criteria that have been used to measure the quality of news reports, and provides a solid foundation for synthesizing the findings of the included studies, while avoiding calculating averages across studies that would be difficult to interpret, if not meaningless.

Screening studies for inclusion in this review and assessing criteria for inclusion in the analysis, which both required significant judgement, were done independently by two reviewers. My background in journalism informed the methods and the interpretation of the

results. And my fluency in Norwegian allowed for including an additional two studies (7% of all included studies), and excluding one study based on the full text (Lote & Aass, 1996).

Limitations

The deviations from the protocol reflect deficiencies in the protocol, particularly related to the third eligibility criterion for studies to be included in the review. That criterion was not sufficiently clear in the protocol. Some of the clarifications made during the review required re-screening records and full texts. In part, weaknesses in the protocol were due to the originality of the question, and a lack of guidance and precedent. However, conducting a pilot using a larger sample of studies, from screening records to grouping criteria, could have saved me and the other reviewers' significant time.

That time could have been spent addressing two other limitations: not translating non-English and non-Norwegian studies; and not screening all reference lists of included studies, or conducting any citations searches. In terms of screening reference lists, I stopped at nine to save time. Three of the 29 studies included in this review (10%) were identified in one of those nine bibliographies, which suggests I will find more eligible studies when I finish screening reference lists, and conduct citation searches, ahead of the planned meta-analysis.

That said, only one of the three included studies identified in reference lists used a tool that was not in one of the 28 other included studies (Woloshin & Schwartz, 2006). In other words, checking about a third of the reference lists contributed one additional tool to the analysis.

Another limitation of the review due to lack of time is that I alone extracted data, and a second reviewer only checked a sample. Based on the check by the second reviewer, who found no important errors, it is unlikely I made many or major mistakes extracting the rest of the data. A second reviewer will check all of the extracted data before the planned meta-analysis.

This review required judgements at several stages: screening records; screening full texts; assessing criteria for inclusion; mapping criteria against the IHC Key Concepts; and grouping criteria. All judgements were made independently by a second reviewer, except judgements about grouping criteria, which were only checked by a second reviewer. Disagreements were easily resolved, but it is possible others would have made different judgements. Nonetheless, the review provides a meaningful overview with important implications, and a solid foundation for synthesising and interpreting the results of the included studies in the planned meta-analysis.

A final important limitation of this review is my definition of quality. The definition was essential for clarity about which studies and criteria would be included or not. However, to help people make informed decisions about health interventions, news reports should also be: factually accurate; appropriate for the target audience; and, ideally, based on the best available evidence. Some criteria that measure quality by these definitions were excluded from this review.

Implications

This review reveals several gaps in the research on the quality of news reports about the effects of health interventions, which should be considered in future studies. The gaps include:

- no studies of the quality of reports about the effects of health systems and policies, despite the enormous impact of such interventions, and
- no studies investigating whether there is a difference in quality between commercial and non-commercial news outlet, despite the logic that suggests an outlet's financial model can impact the quality of reporting, explained in the protocol (Appendix 1), and evidence that it may (Wallington, et al., 2010).

The review also has important implications for the planned meta-analysis. I found researchers used a variety of tools and modified tools to measure quality, and a variety of criteria. This supports the decision to not combine global scores across studies. I also found methodological shortcomings that have implications for synthesising and interpreting the results for individual criteria. The shortcomings include:

- unclear or inadequate categorizing of news reports, for example by medium,
- weaknesses in the development of tools used to measure the quality of reports, and
- weaknesses in terms of the individual criteria.

The unclear or inadequate categorization of news reports needs to be considered before conducting any of the six subgroup analyses planned for in the protocol, to explore variation in the extent to which criteria are satisfied. For example, because news reports published by

newspapers online were in some studies categorized as newspaper reports, trying to compare newspaper reports to reports published in other media may be inappropriate.

Meanwhile, weaknesses in the tools and individual criteria mean the results of the synthesis should be interpreted with caution. Reliability—i.e. whether assessors were measuring the same aspects of quality—was only tested in seven of the included studies (35%). Testing of sensibility (Oxman, et al., 1993, p. 991) or content validity (Heaner, 2009, p. 95)—i.e. whether the tools measure what they are intended to measure—was only described in two studies (7%). Weaknesses in the development of the tools are particularly important when interpreting the results for criteria that require judgement.

There can be a trade-off between how informative a criterion is and how much judgement it requires, or how reliable a criterion is and how sensible. For example, criteria that ask whether study design is mentioned are easy to apply, but not very informative—is the design simply mentioned, or are limitations of the design discussed? On the other hand, criteria that ask whether the quality of the evidence is adequately discussed are more informative, but may be less reliable and more difficult to interpret, since “adequate” requires judgement and it is often unclear how such judgements were made, and therefore unclear whether the same criterion was being used to measure the same aspects of quality within the same study, or the same aspects of quality as similar criteria across studies.

Some criteria were both informative and reliable, for example whether absolute risks are reported. Another possible criterion like this, which was not included in any of the tools, is one that asks whether confidence intervals are reported. Confidence intervals are important for making informed decisions about interventions (Cochrane Effective Practice and

Organisation of Care, 2017), and reporting confidence intervals does not require many words. Moreover, there is a precedent for reporting them given that news reports about polls sometimes include margins of error.

Mapping the criteria against the IHC Key Concepts showed that the tools measure diverse aspects of quality. While some aspects were measured using many different tools, it is unclear how much of a consensus there is about their importance. That they are easy to measure and that other studies have measured them before could also explain their use, at least partially.

There were no criteria that were clearly related to some of the IHC Key Concepts, including concepts that are highly relevant to health information in the news. For example, there were no criteria that mention terms for anecdotal evidence—“case study”, “anecdotal evidence”, “personal experience”—which would relate them to IHC Key Concept 1.2: Anecdotes are unreliable evidence. Personal stories are frequently the subject of health news (Fishman, et al., 2010, p. 516; Mercurio & Elliott, 2011, p. 71; Hurley, et al., 2014, p. 46).

Furthermore, some criteria used in the included studies appear to be inconsistent with IHC Key Concepts, and with the evidence supporting those concepts. For example, some criteria appear inconsistent with IHC Key Concept 2.17: do not confuse “statistical significance” with “importance”. As noted, research findings can be false, even if they are “statistically significant” (Ioannidis, 2005), and the term “statistical significance” is problematic (Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care, 2017).

These issues with the criteria—the trade-off between being informative and requiring judgement, potential heterogeneity where there is lack of clarity, what is not measured, and

the sensibility of what is measured—need to be considered when selecting or developing a tool for new studies, as well as when conducting and interpreting the planned meta-analysis.

Finally, it is important to consider the qualitative evidence from surveys of journalists, and interviews and focus groups with journalists, that shows there are systemic barriers to producing reliable health news (Ashorkhani, et al., 2012; Entwistle, 1995; Larsson, et al., 2003; Pettersen, 2005). It may be difficult if not impossible for journalists to produce reports that satisfy all applicable criteria out of all the criteria included in this review—in a report that people would understand and want to read.

Therefore, any further research should include a careful consideration of what aspects of quality are most important, if the intent is for the results to inform interventions to improve the quality of reporting. On the other hand, the large number of criteria, and the systemic barriers to satisfying them, suggest that rather than trying to improve reporting, we should focus on improving the ability of people to assess health information in the news, and elsewhere.

Conclusion

This was the first review of studies in which researchers have measured the quality of news media reports about the effects of health interventions—i.e. how conducive the reports are to informed decisions about health interventions, or how misleading they are. Twenty-nine studies were included in the review. Two-hundred criteria from the 20 tools used in the studies were considered clear and appropriate measures of quality, as defined for this review.

The included criteria were aggregated in 19 groups, according to the IHC Key Concepts to which they were considered related.

The review revealed gaps in the categories of reports that have been studied. It also revealed methodological weaknesses. In particular, many criteria required substantial judgement and were unclear, several important aspects of quality were not measured by any of the criteria, and some criteria were inconsistent with IHC Key Concepts and the evidence supporting those concepts. These findings have important implications for future studies of the quality of health information in the news media, and other mass media, and for the conduct and interpretation of the planned meta-analysis of results from the included studies.

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Appendix 1: Protocol (including first two appendices)

Abstract

Background: Unreliable information about health care, combined with the inability to assess the reliability of such information, can lead to uninformed decisions and, ultimately, waste and unnecessary suffering. Journalism is a particularly important source of health information. There have been several scientific studies of the quality (reliability) of news media reports about the effects of health interventions. There does not appear to be a systematic review of these studies. The planned review is intended to inform: the production and consumption of health news; as well as further research, including the development of interventions to help people assess health care information in the news, so they can make well-informed decisions.

Objectives: 1) To assess criteria used to measure the quality of news media reports about the effects and costs of health interventions; 2) to assess the quality of such reports; and 3) to explore factors that might explain variation in quality.

Eligibility: We will include scientific studies of print, broadcast and online news reports (the population). At least one explicit criterion must have been used by the researchers to measure quality (the condition). It must be possible and sensible to frame the results for at least one criterion as the proportion of reports that satisfied it (e.g. the proportion of reports in which effect estimates are absolute, not only relative). There will be no limits on language, geography or time period of the reports (the context). To be included, studies must specify: the sampling frame; the selection criteria; and the selection technique.

Methods: Two reviewers will extract data, assess risk of bias, and make judgements about Informed Health Choices (IHC) Key Concepts captured by criteria used in scientific studies. If necessary, a third reviewer will help reach consensus on any judgement. Meta-analyses will be conducted to estimate the prevalence of news reports that satisfy respective criteria. To explore variation, subgroup analyses will be conducted for: medium (broadcast vs. other); time period (decade); financial model (commercial vs. non-commercial); journalist specialisation (health or science vs. other); and country income level (low-income vs. other).

Background

The problem

Unreliable health information

This protocol is for a systematic review that is ultimately intended to help address a major, global problem. The problem has three parts. The first is unreliable health information.

In effect, there is endless information about the effects of health interventions, a health intervention being any action intended to improve or maintain the health of individuals or groups. This includes information about: "modern", "academic", "conventional" or "western" medicine; "complementary", "alternative", "traditional" or "natural" medicine; screening; surgery and devices; diet, exercise and lifestyle; and systems and policies. Some of this information, if not most of it, is unreliable in one way or another. The information can be directly misleading, such as the explicit claim that an intervention causes an outcome when it is only associated with the outcome. Or it can be misleading by omission, such as relative effect estimates without absolute estimates, particularly when the baseline risk is small (Woloshin, et al., 2008).

Researchers have found unreliable lay information about the effects of health interventions in:

- Patient materials (Coulter, et al., 1999); product labels (United States Government Accountability Office, 2010),
- Various types of websites (Culver, et al., 1997; Wolfe, et al., 2002; Glenton, et al., 2005; Spencer, et al., 2016)
- Advertisements (Sansgiry, et al., 1999; Frosch, et al., 2007; Frosch, et al., 2011; Faerber & Kreling, 2013; Groven & Braitwaite, 2016)
- The news (Appendix 1)

Information in the news media is of particular interest, for reasons described later in the background section.

Finally, research referenced in the following subsection shows people are unable to assess information about the effects of health interventions. Logically, if people are unable to assess such information, they are more likely to spread that which is unreliable. Conversely, people spreading unreliable information, as documented in the studies referenced in this subsection, suggests they are unable to assess such information.

Inability to assess health information

The second part of the problem is that people are unable to assess the reliability of information about the effects of health interventions. As part of the Informed Health Choices (IHC) project (www.informedhealthchoices.org), the ability to assess such information and make informed decisions about health interventions has been broken down into the ability to apply specific concepts called the IHC Key Concepts. For example, people need to be able to apply the concept that association is not the same as causation. The original list included 32 concepts (Austvoll-Dahlgren, et al., 2015). The newest iteration includes 36 (Box 1) (Chalmers, et al., 2018). The ability to apply IHC Key Concepts is part of health literacy and has been measured both directly and indirectly.

There have been large surveys of health literacy, in Europe by the European Health Literacy Project Consortium (HLS-EU Consortium, 2013) and in the United States by the National Center for Education Statistics (Kutner, et al., 2006). According to the European survey, "Health literacy is linked to literacy and entails people's knowledge, motivation and competences to access, understand, appraise, and apply health information in order to make judgments and take decisions in everyday life concerning healthcare, disease prevention and health promotion to maintain or improve quality of life during the life course" (HLS-EU Consortium, 2013, p. 7). For the American survey, the term was defined as: "The degree to which individuals have the capacity to obtain, process, and understand basic health information and services needed to make appropriate health decisions" (Kutner, et al., 2006, p. iii).

The ability to apply IHC Key Concepts (i.e. assess the reliability of information about the effects of health interventions and make well-informed decisions) is logically included in both definitions. However, neither survey appears to have objectively measured this. The European survey measured the subjective ease of 47 tasks. Tasks related to applying IHC Key Concepts, including "judge if the information about illness in the media is reliable", were ranked amongst the most difficult (HLS-EU Consortium, 2013).

Box 1: Short titles for the Informed Health Choices (IHC) Key Concepts

Recognising an unreliable basis for a claim

- 1.1. Treatments can harm.
- 1.2. Anecdotes are unreliable evidence.
- 1.3. Association is not the same as causation.
- 1.4. Common practice is not always evidence-based.
- 1.5. Newer is not necessarily better.
- 1.6. Expert opinion is not always right.
- 1.7. Beware of conflicting interests.
- 1.8. More is not necessarily better.
- 1.9. Earlier is not necessarily better.
- 1.10. Hope may lead to unrealistic expectations.
- 1.11. Explanations about how treatments work can be wrong.
- 1.12. Dramatic treatment effects are rare.

Understanding whether comparisons are fair and reliable

- 2.1. Comparisons are needed to identify treatment effects.
- 2.2. Comparison groups should be similar.
- 2.3. Peoples' outcomes should be analysed in their original groups.
- 2.4. Comparison groups should be treated equally.
- 2.5. People should not know which treatment they get.
- 2.6. Peoples' outcomes should be assessed similarly.
- 2.7. All should be followed up.
- 2.8. Consider all the relevant fair comparisons.
- 2.9. Reviews of fair comparisons should be systematic.
- 2.10. Peer review and publication does not guarantee reliable information.
- 2.11. All fair comparisons and outcomes should be reported.
- 2.12. Subgroup analyses may be misleading.
- 2.13. Relative measures of effects can be misleading.
- 2.14. Average measures of effects can be misleading.
- 2.15. Fair comparisons with few people or outcome events can be misleading.
- 2.16. Confidence intervals should be reported.
- 2.17. Do not confuse 'statistical significance' with 'importance'.
- 2.18. Do not confuse 'no evidence of a difference' with 'evidence of no difference'.

Making informed choices

- 3.1. Do the outcomes measured matter to you?
- 3.2. Are you very different from the people studied?
- 3.3. Are the treatments practical in your setting?
- 3.4. Do treatment comparisons reflect your circumstances?
- 3.5. How certain is the evidence?
- 3.6. Do the advantages outweigh the disadvantages?

The American survey suggested a minority of American adults (12%) had “proficient” health literacy (Kutner, et al., 2006, p. v). However, only a sample of the health literacy questions used in that survey are publicly available and none of the available questions measure the ability to assess information about causality (www.nces.ed.gov/NAAL/sample.asp).

Another surrogate measure of people’s ability to apply IHC Key Concepts is their expectations about effects. In a systematic review of patients’ expectations, the majority of participants overestimated benefits and underestimated harms (Hoffmann & Del Mar, 2015). A systematic review of clinicians’ expectations showed clinicians do the same (Hoffmann & Del Mar, 2017).

Other substitutes for ability are attitudes and beliefs. According to a study in the United Kingdom, patients and general practitioners appear to place a disproportionate amount of trust in the reputation of the organisation conducting a clinical trial, the qualifications of the researchers, and peer-review, versus the methods, which are what in fact determine the reliability of the results (The Academy of Medical Sciences, 2016). Moreover, about a third of the respondents (37%) placed a high level of trust in data from medical trials, while about two thirds (65%) placed a high level of trust in the experiences of friends and family, i.e. anecdotal evidence.

There have indeed been studies directly measuring the ability to apply Key Concepts. In Norway, where I am based, Oxman et al. tested a random sample of 626 Norwegian adults (Oxman, et al., 2017). About one in five (19%) showed they were able to distinguish between an association and causation. Other surveys suggest Norwegian students in post-secondary school (Pettersen, 2007) and secondary school (Pettersen, 2005) also struggle with assessing claims about the effects of treatments.

Another product of the Informed Health Choices project is the CLAIM Evaluation Tools database (www.informedhealthchoices.org/claim-evaluation-tools). The CLAIM Evaluation Tools are multiple-choice questions developed specifically to measure people’s ability to apply the IHC Key Concepts (Austvoll-Dahlgren, et al., 2016; Austvoll-Dahlgren, et al., 2017). Before the development of the database, in a systematic review of tools for measuring said ability, Austvoll-Dahlgren et al. identified 215 discrete instruments or procedures, capturing up to 15 of the concepts, whereof four captured 10 or more (Austvoll-Dahlgren, et al., 2016).

A validated set of 26 questions measuring the ability to apply 13 of the concepts (i.e. two questions per concept) were used to measure the effects of IHC learning resources, in two randomised trials (Nsangi, et al., 2017; Semakula, et al.,

2017). In the first trial, the control group was 4430 Ugandan primary school children, after loss to follow-up (Nsangi, et al., 2017). In the second trial, after loss to follow-up, the control group was 273 parents and guardians of children participating in the intervention or control group of the first trial (Semakula, et al., 2017). Less than half of the participants in the control group for either trial answered both questions correctly for any of the 13 included concepts.

Uninformed health decisions

The combination of unreliable information about the effects of health interventions and people's inability to assess such information can result in uninformed decisions. This is the third part of the problem. People acting on unreliable information, or failing to act on reliable advice, can in turn lead to waste and unnecessary suffering. This is why the problem is important.

In a systematic review, low health literacy was found to be associated with worse health outcomes (Berkman, et al., 2011). Granted, what was measured in the included studies, as with the aforementioned surveys of health literacy, may not include the objective ability to apply IHC Key Concepts.

People certainly are making poor decisions. Systematic reviews have found: worldwide overuse of medical services more likely to do harm than good (Brownlee, et al., 2017); underuse of effective services (Glasziou, et al., 2017); and overtesting and undertesting in primary care (O'Sullivan, et al., 2018). Meanwhile, fortunes are spent on "alternative" medicine and dietary supplements without reliable evidence that they are beneficial or safe (Optum, 2013; Starr, 2015). The inability to apply IHC Key Concepts is logically a factor in many of these decisions.

This review

Why do the review?

While I am aware of scientific studies of the quality of news media reports about the effects of health interventions (Appendix 1), I was unable to find a systematic review of such primary studies in Epistemonikos (www.epistemonikos.org), Trip Pro (www.tripdatabase.com), or Google Scholar (www.scholar.google.com), as laid out in Appendix 2. Neither am I aware of a systematic review of how quality has been measured in such studies. Zeraatkar et al. conducted a literature search before developing their own measurement tool, named the Quality Index for health-related Media Reports (QIMR) (2017). However, they only assessed validated tools, and they did not compare criteria to the IHC Key Concepts.

By assessing the methods used to assess quality in eligible studies, the planned review can inform the development and use of methods in further research. By providing an overview of the quality of news media reports about the effects of health interventions, the review can inform the generation of new research questions, for example the geographic focus of those questions.

In two ways, the review can help address the problem of unreliable information about the effects of health interventions, inability to assess that information, and uninformed decisions about the interventions. First, the results can be used to raise awareness about the problem. Second, by showing how news media reports about the effects of health interventions tend to be unreliable (i.e. the specific criteria that the reports tend not to satisfy), the results can inform the prioritisation of IHC Key Concepts when developing interventions to help journalists produce reliable reports and help consumers assess information in the news.

Why focus on the news media?

The news media play a special role in the dissemination of health information. In the United Kingdom, despite an increase in the use of social media, the majority of adults still find out about science most regularly through news media, according to a representative survey of 1,749 adults (Castell, et al., 2014). Granted, the proportion of people finding out about specifically health science through the news may be different.

Meanwhile, Chew and Eysenbach found that in 5395 tweets about the H1N1 outbreak in 2009, most links were to a news website (23%) (Chew & Eysenbach, 2010). Another 12% linked to news blogs, feeds or niche news, compared to 1.5% that linked to government and public health agencies.

While there are other important sources of lay information about the effects of health interventions, including them in this review would be "mixing apples and oranges". In other words, the quality of information in those sources is likely to be significantly different. For example, patient materials are likely to include more information as well as more reliable information than news reports, given that the materials are prepared by health professionals who are trying to inform patients, not attract an audience. The methods used to assess information from different sources may also be different. Furthermore, including sources besides the news media could make the review unwieldy.

Rather, this study can be used to inform reviews focusing on other sources. As stated in the *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions*, there

are pros and cons to both broad and narrow review questions, but with the advent of overviews of systematic reviews, "It may increasingly be considered desirable to plan a series of reviews with a relatively narrow scope, alongside an Overview to summarize their findings" (Higgins & Green, 2011).

Objectives

Primary

1. Assess criteria used to measure the quality of news media reports about the effects and costs of health interventions
2. Assess the quality of news media reports about the effects and costs of health interventions

Secondary

3. Explore factors that might explain variation in quality of news media reports about the effects and costs of health interventions

Eligibility

CoCoPop

Munn et al. note that questions about prevalence do not fit the population, intervention, comparator and outcome (PICO) framework, used for systematic reviews about efficacy (Munn, et al., 2015, pp. 148-149). There is no intervention or exposure, nor is there an outcome on which an intervention or exposure can have an effect. Therefore, instead of the PICO framework, I will use the mnemonic CoCoPop (condition, context, and population) to set inclusion criteria, as Munn et al. recommend. I have added criteria for study design, as per the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) statement (Moher, et al., 2015).

Population

In *News Around the World: Content, Practitioners and the Public*, Shoemaker and Cohen write: “[The journalist] typically constructs a method for fulfilling the daily job requirements. He or she rarely has an underlying theoretical understanding of what defining something or someone as newsworthy entails” (Shoemaker & Cohen, 2006, p. 7). In other words, even journalists will struggle to tell you what exactly “news” is. This includes me.

In *A history of news*, Stephens uses the definition: “New information about a subject of some public interest that is shared with some portion of the public” (Stephens, 2007, p. 4). In terms of the review, applying such a broad definition would be problematic in several ways. For example, advertisements, press releases and journal articles could all be considered news.

Instead of using a specific definition, I will be pragmatic. I will only consider studies of information that: 1) is in newspapers or magazines (print), radio, podcasts or television (broadcast) or news websites (online); and 2) is labelled by the authors as “news” or any common synonym. In terms of online, I will focus on dedicated news websites, i.e. not social media platforms, although news reports appear on such platforms.

I will only include studies of reports about the potential health effects (negative or positive changes in health outcomes) and the monetary costs of health interventions (any action intended to improve or maintain the health of an individual or group). The reports can all be about the same condition or intervention, or they can be a mix.

If an otherwise eligible study’s sample includes news reports about the effects of health interventions as well as other types of news reports, I will extract data

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only about the former, if possible. Otherwise, I will leave out the study and list it in a table of excluded studies. In the same table, I will list any studies of the quality of other health information in news reports, besides information about the effects of health interventions.

Condition

By “quality”, I mean an attribute that is either conducive to informed decisions about health interventions (e.g. presents potential effects in absolute numbers) or misleading (e.g. only presents potential effects in relative numbers), or the sum of such attributes. The condition of my population—news media reports—is either having satisfied at least one explicit criterion for quality or not (e.g. either presenting potential effects in absolute numbers or not).

In potentially eligible primary studies of which I am aware (Appendix 1), researchers have used different sets of criteria to measure quality. Zeraatkar et al. conducted a literature search before developing their own tool to measure the quality of reporting on health research, named the Quality Index for health-related Media Reports (QIMR) (2017). They identified one other validated tool with the same purpose, named the Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ) (Oxman, et al., 1993). They also identified and assessed instruments for measuring the quality of patient information: Ensuring Quality Information for Patients (EQIP) (Moult, et al., 2004) and DISCERN (Charnock, et al., 1999). Zeraatkar et al. concluded that both EQIP and DISCERN have poor content relevance to health news reports.

It would be problematic to restrict the review to studies that use either the QIMR or ISQ to measure quality. This would exclude studies of reports where the health information is not based on research—e.g. information based on anecdotal evidence. Moreover, the QIMR was published as recently as 2017, and in most of the potentially eligible studies of which I am aware, neither the QIMR or the ISQ were used to measure quality. In several studies, researchers have used criteria based on those used by Moynihan et al. (Moynihan, et al., 2000)—e.g. Smith et al. (2005). In other studies, researchers have developed and used their own tools, e.g. Marcon et al. (2017). A criterion may be sensible even if the tool was not validated, and it may be sensible to group the criterion with others for meta-analysis.

Context

The population for the review is limited to news in the aforementioned mediums: newspapers and magazines; radio, podcasts and television; and news websites. I will not set any limits in terms of geography, language or time period.

Study design

For a study to be eligible, the results must include dichotomous or categorical data for at least one explicit criterion used to measure quality. It must be possible to dichotomise the data as either satisfying the criterion or not, for two reasons: to ensure the results can be easily interpreted, and to synthesise findings across studies.

Some nuance, such as the number of reports that “partially” satisfy a criterion, may be lost in this synthesis. The importance of such detail is questionable; if a quality is important enough to be measured, the criterion used to measure that quality should be clearly satisfied, assuming it is relevant to the specific report.

Studies that only provide a global quality score, such as a star rating, will be excluded and listed in the table of excluded studies. Global scores are difficult to interpret, since they do not tell you which parts of a news report are problematic. Furthermore, they are difficult to compare across studies using different scoring systems.

To be included, studies must specify: the sampling frame (i.e. where the news reports were sampled from); the selection criteria for the reports; and the selection technique. This excludes case studies of single reports. I will list any case studies that would otherwise be eligible in the table of excluded studies.

Methods

Search strategy

To make sure my search is systematic and transparent, I will base my approach on the guideline developed by Kable et al. (2012). As noted in the description of my search for an existing review (Appendix 2), while my question is interdisciplinary, I consider it unlikely that a systematic review designed to answer it would have been published in an academic journal focused on journalism. However, I consider it more likely that an eligible primary study has been published in such a journal. Therefore, in addition to PubMed (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed), I will search Google Scholar (www.scholar.google.com) and Scopus (www.scopus.com). I will search for grey literature in Open Grey (www.opengrey.eu) and Grey Literature Report (www.greylit.org), as well as theses in ProQuest Dissertations & Theses (Global Full text plus UK and Ireland abstracts) (www.proquest.com). I will not place limits on language or time period in any of my searches.

In the search for an existing review, I only included terms for the population (news media reports) when searching Epistemonikos and Trip Pro, since I could filter for systematic reviews, which reduced the results to a manageable number. In the upcoming search for primary studies, given there is not a reliable filter I can use for study design, I will also include terms for the condition (quality) or terms related to the analysis, to improve the specificity of the search strategy.

I will identify additional terms for the PubMed search, including Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms, by looking up the studies in PubMed or, if the study is not in PubMed, in another database, and extracting relevant terms. The aim is to ensure my search captures all studies of which I am aware, as well as similar studies. I will also add terms for specific categories of media (e.g. print). I will conduct test searches to inform pragmatic decisions about editing or dropping terms, with the aim of making the search and screening as efficient as possible, while minimising the risk of missing eligible studies. I will use the PubMed search as the basis for searches in other databases.

Besides searching databases, I will check the reference lists of eligible studies. In Scopus, I will screen studies citing those that are eligible, as well as studies citing the development of the ISQ or the QIMR. I will take advantage of my professional network, conducting targeted dissemination of the protocol via email and broad dissemination via Twitter, to crowdsource eligible studies. Finally, I will contact the authors of eligible studies and the developers of the ISQ and QIMR, to ask about unpublished studies.

Study language is not an eligibility criterion, but to be pragmatic, I will only search English language databases. To screen any studies without an English abstract for eligibility, I will use Google Translate (www.translate.google.com). If necessary, I will seek help from someone fluent in the language e.g. an acquaintance or one of the authors. To extract data from a non-English paper, I will again seek help. In the excluded studies table, I will list any apparently eligible studies from which I am unable to extract data because of a language barrier or because of inadequate reporting and inability to obtain missing information from the authors.

A second reviewer and I will independently judge eligibility by reviewing each abstract and, if necessary, (sections of) the full text. Appendix 3 is the form we will use to confirm eligibility. Any disagreements will be discussed before moving on to data extraction and assessment of risk of bias. A third reviewer will be brought in to arbitrate if necessary.

Data extraction

A second reviewer and I will independently extract data about the population, study design, criteria used to assess the quality of the reports, and the results. We will again discuss any disagreements, bringing in a third reviewer to arbitrate if necessary. Appendix 4 is the form we will use to extract data about population and design. Appendix 5 is the separate spreadsheet in which we will enter the individual criteria and results for each criterion.

I have determined what data to extract based on what is reported in the potentially eligible studies of which I am aware (Appendix 1), various tools (Vandenbroucke, et al., 2007; The Joanna Briggs Institute, 2014; Moher, et al., 2015; Munn, et al., 2015), my expertise, and common sense. Appendix 6 contains dummy tables for all the data to be extracted, as well as the risk of bias assessments and analyses.

Population

A second reviewer and I will extract data about the following variables, in terms of the samples of news reports: medium of publication; geographic area of publication; time period of publication; category of intervention reported on; and whether the outlet is commercial or not. In terms of medium, radio and podcasts will be one category, in addition to the categories: newspapers; magazines; television; and news websites. The nine predetermined categories of intervention are: "modern" medicine (aka. "academic", "conventional" or "Western" medicine); "alternative" medicine (aka. "complementary", "traditional" or "natural" medicine); screening; surgery; devices; diet; exercise; lifestyle; and systems and policies.

Study design

For each study, we will record: the instrument used to measure quality; the stated objectives; the sampling frame; the selection criteria and technique; and any reported subgroup analyses.

Criteria, response options and results

Finally, we will record each eligible criterion used to assess the quality of reports, as well as the response options, in a spreadsheet separate from the form used to collect data about the population and study design (Appendix 5). We will enter the results for each criterion into the same spreadsheet. Where data are available for subgroups of news reports, we will record the overall results and the results for each subgroup.

Assessing risk of bias

In a systematic review of tools used to assess the quality of prevalence studies and other observational research, Shamliyan et al. identified 46 scales and 51 checklist, none of which discriminated between reporting versus methodological quality, or external versus internal validity (2010). Through citation searches, I identified several tools developed after the review, of which I have chosen to use the latest, developed by Munn et al. (2014), as a starting point, based on face validity and simplicity. While Munn et al. do not refer to the review by Shamliyan and colleagues, they compare their tool to one developed by Hoy et al. (2012) who do consider said review. The critical appraisal tool developed by Munn et al. includes ten items, with the response options "Yes", "No", "Unclear" and "Not applicable":

1. Was the sample representative of the target population?
2. Were study participants recruited in an appropriate way?
3. Was the sample size adequate?
4. Were the study subjects and the setting described in detail?
5. Was the data analysis conducted with sufficient coverage of the identified sample?
6. Were objective, standard criteria used for the measurement of the condition?
7. Was the condition measured reliably?
8. Was there appropriate statistical analysis?
9. Are all important confounding factors/subgroups/differences identified and accounted for?
10. Were subpopulations identified using objective criteria?

Of the ten items, three assess risk of bias and are relevant and applicable to this review: items 2, 6 and 7. Item 2 assesses risk of selection bias, while items 6 and 7 measure detection bias (aka. Information bias). Focusing on these two types of bias is consistent with the Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) statement (Vandenbroucke, et al., 2007, p. 814) and methods used by the Cochrane Methodology Review Group to systematically review the prevalence of a condition in a population of information, as opposed to people (Welch, et al., 2010, p. 7).

A second reviewer and I will independently assess risk of bias in each study, criterion by criterion, given that some criteria used to measure the quality of news reports require more subjective judgement than others. These assessments will be used to describe the strengths and weaknesses of the studies. If deemed necessary, they will also be used to conduct a sensitivity analysis. It is unclear how

a greater risk of bias would impact the results of studies to be included in this review, so I have no hypothesis about the results of such an analysis.

In terms of selection bias, if the news reports were randomly or sequentially sampled from the target population, we will consider the risk of bias as low. If the reports were purposively sampled, we will consider the risk of bias as high. If any other sampling technique was used, we will consider the risk of bias as moderate or high.

In terms of detection bias, if a criterion requires minimal judgement (e.g. a criterion that risks be presented in absolute numbers), we will consider the risk of bias as low. If the criterion requires substantial judgement (e.g. whether there is sufficient information about potential harms), two researchers assessed the reports, and they were blinded to the journalist and publication, we will consider the risk of bias as moderate. If the criterion requires substantial judgement, and only one researcher assessed the reports or researchers assessing the reports were not blinded to the journalist and publication, we will consider the risk of bias as high.

If the risk of either selection or detection bias is high, we will consider the overall risk of bias as high. If the risk of either is moderate, we will consider the risk as moderate. Appendix 6 includes a dummy table for the risk of bias assessments. Appendix 7 is the form that we will use to assess risk of bias. It includes a space for recording any conflicts of interests. Any such conflicts will be discussed separately when interpreting the results of the review.

Analyses

Criteria used to measure quality

How quality has been measured will be assessed by comparing criteria to the IHC Key Concepts (Box 1). Each eligible criterion from each study will be entered into a spreadsheet, diagonally across from the full concept list (Appendix 8). A second reviewer and I will judge which concepts are captured by each criterion, representing the judgements with marks in the spreadsheet. We will discuss any agreements and bring in a third researcher to arbitrate, if necessary.

The IHC Key Concepts differ from other lists of criteria for making causal inferences in two ways (Chalmers, et al., 2018, pp. 30-31). First, the list is different in that it is both: a) developed using a systematic, transparent and iterative process; and b) intended to help children, the general public and health practitioners make informed decisions, not just health researchers. Second, unlike other tools such as checklists and tip sheets, it is not an intervention in and of itself, limited to a particular population or context, but a comprehensive framework that can be used for mapping skills, developing interventions and evaluating interventions.

Using the IHC Key Concept list to assess the criteria used to measure quality of the news reports has several advantages. First, it provides a framework for grouping criteria from different studies, so results can more easily be synthesised. Second, it will shed light on relevant qualities that have not typically been measured or measured at all. Conversely, it may reveal concepts captured by

the criteria missing from the IHC Key Concept list. Finally, using the list can inform the interpretation of results from this review, including what the results suggest about what concepts are most important when developing interventions for improving reporting on the effects of interventions, or helping people assess information in such reports.

A second reviewer and I will judge what criteria used in different studies can be grouped. Once more, we will discuss any disagreements and bring in a third reviewer to arbitrate if necessary.

Quality of news reports

As far as the data permits, we will meta-analyse the proportions of samples that either satisfied or failed to satisfy respective criteria, i.e. the prevalence of reports satisfying or failing to satisfy a given criterion. See dummy tables in Appendix 6. We will dichotomise categorical data where possible and sensible. Furthermore, we may reframe data that already is dichotomous as satisfying or not satisfying a given criterion.

Not satisfying a criterion will include anything other than completely satisfying it. In other words, if news reports “partially” satisfy a criterion or it is unclear whether the reports satisfy it, we will consider the reports as not having satisfied the criterion. If a criterion has been deemed inapplicable to reports, we will exclude those reports from the meta-analysis for that criterion. In addition to potentially giving us larger samples for meta-analysis, the dichotomisation will make interpreting the results more straightforward.

Across studies, I anticipate reports will generally fail to satisfy most criteria, despite differences in populations and methods. Therefore, I expect mean proportions with 95% confidence intervals will be meaningful. I will prepare forest plots and visually analyse the extent to which there are meaningful differences between point estimates, and I will conduct a Chi-square test to see if the heterogeneity is larger than one would expect by chance. For a given criterion, if the visual interpretation and Chi-square test suggest it is appropriate, I will conduct a meta-analysis using a random effects model. I will also conduct six subgroup analyses, when data are available.

Variation in quality

Again, I do not expect a lot of variation in the quality of reports across studies. To the extent that there is variation, I do not expect a lot of data for exploring it. That said, there are several variables that could logically explain variation, evidence supporting some of those hypotheses, and reasons to test them.

Table 1 is an overview of: the variables for which we will conduct subgroup analyses; the subgroups; the hypothesised differences; and the rationales for the hypotheses and for conducting the analyses. The variables are: the medium in which a report was published; the time period in which a report was published; whether the publishing outlet was commercial; whether the journalist was specialised in health or science; and the income level of the country in which the outlet is situated.

On the one hand, I will be cautious about extrapolating findings if there is no direct evidence for a subpopulation (e.g. broadcast reports) and there is reason to be uncertain about the applicability of the evidence from other subpopulations (e.g. print and online reports). On the other hand, subgroup analyses are frequently misleading, as shown by Sun et al. (2014).

To avoid spurious results, we will use explicit criteria for assessing the credibility of any difference, based on Sun and colleagues' criteria:

- The difference is of practical importance.
- The difference is bigger than we would expect by chance.
- The difference is in the hypothesised direction.
- The difference is unlikely to be explained by other known variables.
- The difference is consistent across studies with different methods.
- The difference is consistent across studies with different outcome measures.
- The difference is consistent across studies with different levels of risk of bias.

For each explanatory variable, given sufficient data, we will conduct univariate regression analyses with the variable (e.g. medium) as the independent variable, and with the proportion of subpopulations (e.g. reports from respective decades) that satisfy the criterion as the dependent variable. We will also conduct multiple regression analyses with all of the explanatory variables. We will note any within-study subgroup analyses where the researchers have used appropriate statistical methods or provided the necessary data for us to do an appropriate statistical analysis ourselves. We will consider those analyses when making judgements about the credibility of subgroup differences.

I have decided against conducting a subgroup analysis for the type of report, i.e. whether the report is a feature or a breaking news report. Features are typically longer in words and prepared on longer deadlines. They might logically be higher quality than breaking news reports. However, an analysis by type of report would likely be confounded by medium, financial model, and specialisation. Furthermore, how researchers have defined feature versus breaking news, and how they have measured length of report or deadline, may be so different across studies that combining the data would not make sense.

Table 1: Subgroup analyses

Variable	Grouping	Hypothesis	Rationale and importance
Medium	Broadcast vs. other (print and online)	Broadcast reports are less likely to satisfy criteria	Broadcast allows for fewer words, as well as less time for writing, given time spent recording and editing. This would logically have a negative impact on the quality of reports. I am aware of empirical evidence that supports this hypothesis (Walsh-Childers, et al., 2016). A credible difference in the hypothesised direction would imply consumers should pay less attention to broadcast reports.
Time period	Decades (≥2000; 1990-1999; 1980-1989; etc.)	The proportion of reports satisfying criteria is likely to be similar across decades	On the one hand, news reports may have improved since the advent of "evidence-based medicine" (EBM) (Evidence-Based Medicine Working Group, 1992). On the other, there are sustained, systemic barriers to reliable health journalism such as lack of time (Larsson, et al., 2003; Pettersen, 2005), which EBM does not address. Moreover, revenue losses may have led news media to invest less in strategies that might improve the quality of their health news, such as training journalists and editors, and hiring and retaining specialised health and science reporters. However, a credible improvement for one or more criteria would be an impetus for research to explain said improvement, and that research could inform the development of interventions to improve quality overall.
Financial model	Commercial vs. non-commercial	Reports published by commercial outlets are less likely to satisfy criteria	The financial interests of commercial outlets may lead to sensationalism, to attract audiences (Larsson, et al., 2003; Pettersen, 2005; Wallington, et al., 2010). Moreover, companies that sell health interventions may be advertisers, disincentivising critical reporting. A credible difference in the hypothesised direction would imply consumers should support non-commercial outlets and pay less attention to reports published by commercial outlets.
Specialisation	Health and science journalists vs. other	Reports prepared by health or science journalists are more likely to satisfy criteria	Journalist who have specialised in health or science are more likely to have received training in critical appraisal. Moreover, compared to other journalists, they may have been in more contact with scientists, and may be more familiar with the language, content and structure of research papers. There is evidence that journalists with more advanced degrees are more likely to use scientific journal articles as sources, and that journalists with fewer years of experience are more likely to say providing entertainment is an important priority for health news (Wallington, et al., 2010). A credible difference in the hypothesised direction would imply consumers should pay more attention to reports prepared by specialised health and science journalists.
Country income level	Low-income countries vs. other (middle and high-income countries)	The proportion of reports satisfying criteria is likely to be similar across countries with different income levels	While news media in middle and high-income countries may have more resources, journalists in those countries still face systemic barriers to high-quality reporting (Larsson, et al., 2003; Pettersen, 2005; Wallington, et al., 2010). Support for this hypothesis would suggest researchers should develop interventions that can improve the quality of reporting in low-income countries and middle or high-income countries alike. It would also imply those interventions address barriers beside lack of resources.
Newspaper type	Broadsheet vs. tabloid	Reports in broadsheet newspapers are more likely to satisfy criteria	Reporting in tabloid newspapers may be less detailed and more sensational than reporting in broadsheet newspapers, and I am aware of evidence that the quality of reports about the effects of health interventions is lower in tabloids (Entwistle & Hancock-Beaulieu, 1992; Robinson, et al., 2013). A credible difference in the hypothesised direction would imply consumers should pay more attention to broadsheet newspapers, and less to tabloids.

Pilot

Having conducted the search, we will pilot forms, spreadsheets and tables (Appendixes 3 through 6) on the first five eligible studies. We will discuss any issues and make any revisions deemed necessary before completing data extraction, risk of bias assessments and analyses for remaining studies.

Rating the quality of the evidence

I have adjusted the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach to rating the quality of evidence (Guyatt, et al., 2008). The GRADE approach involves considering five factors for lowering the certainty of evidence: study limitations, inconsistency of results, indirectness of evidence, imprecision, and publication bias. I have adjusted these, given that GRADE was developed for research about effects, not prevalence. Appendix 9 is the form we will use to rate the quality of the evidence.

The first adjustment is that we will not consider publication bias. I am not aware of any research documenting publication bias for prevalence or incidence studies generally, nor specifically in this area. Besides, I expect too few studies and samples that are too small for it to be meaningful to assess the risk of publication bias.

Second, we will not consider directness since it is inapplicable. I will, however, be cautious about extrapolating evidence across subpopulations specified in Table 1 (e.g. across reports from different time periods), if there is no evidence for one of the subpopulations specific (e.g. reports from before a particular decade).

This leaves considering risk of bias, imprecision and inconsistency. In terms of imprecision, we will use quartiles as a rule of thumb; if the confidence interval substantially crosses two or more quartiles, we will consider there to be important imprecision, following guidance developed by the Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC) group (Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care, 2017). GRADE factors for increasing the certainty of the evidence are not relevant here.

Ethical considerations and conflicts of interest

The review does not involve particular ethical challenges. I declare that I have no relevant conflicts of interest.

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Appendix 1: Reference list of potentially eligible studies

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Appendix 2: Description of search for an existing review

Before drafting the protocol, I searched to see if there is a systematic review that has already answered the research question: What is the quality of news media reports about the effects and costs of health interventions? The question is interdisciplinary. However, I consider it unlikely that such a review has been published in a journal focused on journalism. This is based on my experience and knowledge from studying and working in both journalism and health research. Moreover, I was aware of more than 30 potentially eligible primary studies before searching for an existing review (Appendix 1), and all of those studies were published in the health-focused databases that I searched.

Specifically, I searched the meta-databases Epistemonikos (www.epistemonikos.org) and Trip Pro (www.tripdatabase.com). These include PubMed (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed), the Cochrane Library (www.cochranelibrary.com) and Prospero (www.crd.york.ac.uk/prospero). It is unlikely that a health-related systematic review with such broad relevance would be missing from such large databases of health-related systematic reviews.

No limits were placed on time of publication or language. The Epistemonikos search was limited to titles and abstracts. The Trip Pro search was limited to titles only, since Trip Pro searches cannot be limited to abstracts. Neither Epistemonikos or Trip Pro have Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) functionality. In both searches, I only used terms for the population because I considered those terms sufficiently narrow, given that I could filter for systematic reviews.

I identified and selected terms for the population in six steps. First, I checked for terms in the titles of potentially eligible studies. Second, I broke down compounds (e.g. "news media reports") into smaller terms (e.g. "news", "media" and "reports"). Third, I checked a thesaurus for synonyms. Fourth, I listed the smaller terms and what I considered common synonyms. Fifth, I placed the list along both the top and left side of a table, and considered all possible combinations, excluding those that are nonsensical or uncommon (Appendix 2a). Finally, I selected terms from the table, considering: 1) how likely it was that someone would have used the given term to describe the population in a review

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answering the research question; and 2) how many irrelevant search results using the term would add.

I got feedback from an information specialist on an initial draft of the search strategy, then conducted test searches. In some cases, the test searches were for single terms. Some of those single terms, such as “media” and “mass media”, were excluded from the final searches. Including them would have added a large number of irrelevant search results—for example reviews related to (mass) media interventions, such as interventions for smoking cessation—and I considered it unlikely that a review answering the research question would exclude all of the remaining terms from its title.

The only difference between the terms used in the Epistemonikos and Trip Pro searches was that “the news” was excluded from the Trip Pro search (Table A1). Excluding the term reduced the results by over 1000. The problem appears to have been that the engine automatically and irreversibly included similar, but inaccurate and broad terms, including “new”.

The final Epistemonikos search resulted in 89 entries categorised as systematic reviews (Appendix 2b). The final Trip Pro search resulted in 48 (Appendix 2c). Both searches were executed on Feb. 19, 2018. Neither resulted in a systematic review answering the research question.

To test my assumption about the (un)likelihood of there being a systematic review answering the question in a journal focused on journalism, I searched Google Scholar (www.scholar.google.com) on the same date, screening the first 50 results. Since there is a Google Scholar searches have a character limit, I only used “news” to describe the population, while adding “health” and “systematic review” (Table A1). Limiting the search to titles (i.e. typing “allintitle:” ahead of the search terms) only resulted in one entry, which did not answer the research question. Removing said limit increased the results to 6990 entries. Of the first 50, most were in health-focused or health-related journals, several were familiar from Epistemonikos and Trip Pro searches, and none answered the research question.

In addition to the database searches, I consulted with four other researchers who have done studies related to the quality of health journalism, and who have taught “evidence-based” health journalism. Three are co-authors of studies potentially eligible primary studies. They were all unaware of a systematic review answering the research question.

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Table A1: Terms used to search for an existing systematic review answering the research question

Database	Query
Epistemonikos	(title:(("media coverage" OR "news coverage" OR "press coverage" OR "fourth estate" OR "media information" OR "news items" OR "journalis*" OR "lay media" OR "news media" OR "health news" OR "the news" OR "media outlets" OR "news outlets" OR "press outlets" OR "lay press" OR "popular press" OR "the press" OR "media reporting" OR "news reporting" OR "media reports" OR "news reports" OR "media sources" OR "news sources" OR "health stories" OR "media stories" OR "news stories")) OR abstract:(("media coverage" OR "news coverage" OR "press coverage" OR "fourth estate" OR "media information" OR "news items" OR "journalis*" OR "lay media" OR "news media" OR "health news" OR "the news" OR "media outlets" OR "news outlets" OR "press outlets" OR "lay press" OR "popular press" OR "the press" OR "media reporting" OR "news reporting" OR "media reports" OR "news reports" OR "media sources" OR "news sources" OR "health stories" OR "media stories" OR "news stories")))
Trip Pro	title:(("media coverage" OR "news coverage" OR "press coverage" OR "fourth estate" OR "media information" OR "news items" OR "journalis*" OR "lay media" OR "news media" OR "health news" OR "media outlets" OR "news outlets" OR "press outlets" OR "lay press" OR "popular press" OR "the press" OR "media reporting" OR "news reporting" OR "media reports" OR "news reports" OR "media sources" OR "news sources" OR "health stories" OR "media stories" OR "news stories"))
Google Scholar	health "systematic review" "news media"

Appendix 2: Additional search strings

A2 Table 1: Google Scholar search string 1 of 3, June 21, 2018

allintitle: health news quality

A2 Table 2: Google Scholar search string 2 of 3, June 22, 2018

allintitle: health news

A2 Table 3: Google Scholar search string 3 of 3, June 22, 2018

health news quality

A2 Table 4: Open Grey search string, June 22, 2018

health news

A2 Table 5: Grey Literature Report search string, refined to search within titles only, June 22, 2018

news

A2 Table 6: ProQuest Dissertations & Theses (Global Full text plus UK and Ireland abstracts) search string 1 of 2, refined to search within titles onl, June 22, 2018

noft(health) AND noft(news) AND noft(quality)

A2 Table 7: ProQuest Dissertations & Theses (Global Full text plus UK and Ireland abstracts) search string 2 of 2, refined to search within titles only, June 22, 2018

noft(health) AND noft(news) AND noft(accuracy)

Appendix 3: Study objectives, sampling frames, and selection criteria and techniques

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Andrew et al. 2016	"We sought to characterize the accuracy of media and Internet reporting of practice-changing clinical trials in oncology." (p. 269)	The New York Times, The Wall Street Journal, and The Globe and Mail (newspapers), and cnn.com, foxnews.com, and ctv.ca (TV) (p. 270)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Reporting on the conference proceeding and/or abstract for the [clinical cancer advances]" (p. 270)	"Every term—cancer subtype AND drug name OR procedure name—was searched for when using each electronic resource" (p. 270)
Basu et al. 2008	"To explore the quality (accuracy, balance, practical context) of tabloid articles reporting on nutrition research, and public attitudes towards it." (p. 1124)	The Sun, Daily Mirror, Daily Star, Daily Mail, and Daily Express (newspapers) (p. 1126)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Reporting on nutrition research and providing a traceable source to the original research (journal name, author and/or organisation)" (p. 1126) <i>Exclusion:</i> "Where the original research could not be obtained" (p. 1126)	"Newspapers were purchased and examined daily" (p. 1226)
Bonevski et al. 2008	"This paper aims to examine the type and quality of health news reports about [complementary and alternative medicine] in the Australian media." (p. 1)	Sydney Morning herald, The Australian, The Age, The Daily Telegraph, The Courier Mail, Sunday Telegraph, The Sun Herald, and Herald Sun (newspapers), ABC online, and ninemsn (news websites), and Nine's "A current Affair" and Seven's "Today tonight" (TV) (p. 2)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Made therapeutic claims about new treatments, procedures and diagnostic tests" (p. 2)	"Identified by daily web site searches by a research assistant" (p. 2)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Bubela et al. 2008	Not stated explicitly	British, Irish, American, Australian and New Zealand newspaper reports via Lexis/Nexis, and Canadian newspaper reports via Factiva (p. 2)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Discussed the results of an identifiable, published clinical trial" (p. 2)	"We first searched [using] using the search term '(herb or herbal) and remedy and 'clinical trial' [...] As many newspaper articles do not use the expression 'clinical trial' but instead use terms such as 'study', we also conducted specific searches on Lexis/Nexis and Factiva for additional newspaper articles on each clinical trial using different combinations of search terms, including journal name, author name(s), herbal remedy tested, and lead research institution. We omitted duplicate newspaper articles, selecting the article with highest word count, to take into account the effect of syndicated articles and newswires [...] One author (HB) with expertise in pharmacology identified corresponding pharmaceuticals for each medical condition identified in the coded herbal remedy clinical trials. We conducted searches on Lexis/Nexis and Factiva as above for newspaper coverage of identifiable clinical trials of the pharmaceuticals. As significantly more pharmaceutical trials received press coverage, we randomly selected up to three clinical trials per medical condition and then repeated the specific newspaper searches and coding methodology as above." (p. 2)
Cassels et al. 2003	Not stated explicitly	"24 of Canada's largest daily newspapers, with weekday circulations of greater than 50 000 (22 English and 2 French, from 6 provinces) [...] Fourteen [via] Infomart's Special Edition, [three via] Virtual News Library, [three via] Eureka and [two via] The Globe & Mail database." (p. 1134)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Discussed at least one beneficial or harmful effect of any of the study's 5 drugs" (p. 1134)	"We performed a key word search using the brand and generic names of the 5 drugs [...] Each article was stripped of its title, source, date and byline [sic] and was then assigned a study code. For each stripped article, 2 members of the research team manually, and independently of each other, reviewed the article's content to determine its suitability for inclusion in the study; a third member arbitrated any differences." (p. 1134)
Hackman and Moe 1999	Not stated explicitly	Weekday articles in The New York Times, The Wall Street Journal, The Seattle Times, USA Today, and Los Angeles Times, via DataTimes (p. 1564)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Reader could locate the original study from information reported in the newspaper" (p. 1564)	"Searching Data times [...] Key search words included "study" and any 1 or more of the following: "diet," "nutrition," "caffeine," "cholesterol," "fat," "vitamins," "minerals," "antioxidants," and "exercise." Second, we manually searched The New York Times and The Seattle Times for 6 months and The Wall Street Journal for 2 months to verify the completeness of the key word search." (p. 1564)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Haneef et al. 2015	"We aimed to describe and assess the frequency of spin in news items reporting the results of studies evaluating an intervention that are highlighted in the health section of Google News." (p. 2)	Health section of Google News, US, UK and Canada editions (news websites) (p. 3)	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> "Referred to a published study evaluating the effect of a treatment (pharmacological or non-pharmacological treatment) on human health regardless of study design. We also included any article published in any non-medical journal." (p. 3)</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> "Reported 1) studies of correlation, screening, diagnostic, prognostic, case reports, guidelines and vaccine development; 2) highlighted the results of studies reported as an abstract or a poster presented in a scientific meeting or were unpublished; and 3) reported 2 or more scientific studies in one news item" (p. 3)</p>	"One researcher (RH) screened all the headlines of news appearing in the health section of Google News" (p. 3)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Heaner 2009	“The purpose of this study is twofold: to describe the accuracy and other characteristics of the reporting of nutrition and physical-activity-related coverage in six major American newspapers during 2008. Information” (p. 12)	USA Today, The Wall Street Journal, The New York Times, The Los Angeles Times, The Washington Post, and The New York Post (newspapers) (p. 75)	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> “Reporting on one main nutrition-, physical-activity, or obesity-related study. One or more studies may be referred to in the text, but the purpose of the article was to highlight the findings of one specific study, rather than report on a broad nutrition or physical-activity-related issue” (p. 78)</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> "Fell into one of the following categories: (a) a repeated citation of the same article (b) an editorial/commentary (c) a letter to the editor (d) an obituary (e) an event or TV listing (f) a sports column concerning the practices of particular athletes (g) recipes or cooking columns (h) an online-only article (it did not appear in the printed version of the paper) (i) an article appearing in a weekly magazine accompanying the newspaper (j) articles reporting on historical issues (such as artifacts) (k) a film, theatre, restaurant or entertainment-type review" (p. 78)</p>	"Two electronic databases, LexisNexis Academic (Dayton, OH) and ProQuest Newspapers, were used to retrieve articles [...] Keywords entered into both databases were: 'study OR research AND nutrition OR diet OR obesity OK fitness OR physical activity OR exercise' [...] After entering keywords into both databases, the list of citations (N= 3578) generated were reviewed. Citations provided the following information for each article: title, section of the newspaper, newspaper name, date, page number and reporter name. Articles that did not meet the study criteria (see Table 8) based on this information were excluded [...] Next, each article was read in its entirety to confirm eligibility" (p. 77-8)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002	Not stated explicitly	Newspaper reports in Aftenposten, Bergens Tidende, Dagbladet and Norsk Telegrambyrå via a-tekst, and in Stavanger Aftenblad and Fædrelandsvennen via “local text archives” (p. 1672)	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> ["One or more of the following should be satisfied: The re mentions and/or considers the medication’s effect and/or side-effect, beyond mentioning what the medication is used for/the medication’s indication; The article mentions effect and/or side-effect of a whole class of medications, and it says our medication belongs to this class; The article mentions the medication’s cost for the consumer or health service; The article mentions publicly subsidized prescription or right to reimbursement for our medication”] (p. 1672)</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> ["One or more: The article is of “question and answer” or “Dear Doctor” format; The article is a letter to the editor, an editorial, or a personal ad or any other type of article that is not produced by the newspaper staff; The article is a preview of a TV or radio programme; The discussion of pros and/or cons is only about usage clearly outside of the area of indication; The medication is discussed only as metaphor, comparison, joke, or anecdote”] (p. 1672)</p>	["All articles that contained one of the brand names of were obtained.”] (p. 1672)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Iaboli et al. 2010	"The aim of the present study was twofold: on one hand, we asked whether similar journalistic shortcomings may be observable also when taking into account articles dealing with health-related topics other than the introduction of new prescription drugs or the description of the hottest medical breakthroughs. On the other hand, we attempted to adopt a wider explorative approach with respect to previous studies by evaluating health news reporting by all (Italian) national newspapers." (p. 2)	Italian national daily newspapers and weekly magazines "listed in the Italian [Accertamenti Diffusione Stampa] print certification," excluding "sports newspapers [...] obituaries, book reviews, articles about health ethics, politics or economy, readers' letters, reports on injuries, juridical [sic] and police inquiries, announcements of future conferences, well-being/fitness articles and medical advertisements" (p. 2)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Properly meeting with the definition of health science communication articles, i.e., articles supposedly aiming at improving the reader's knowledge on health-related topics from a scientific perspective" (p. 2)	"Through Nograziapagoio (http://www.nograziapagoio.it), an organization similar to US No Free Lunch, dealing with conflicts of interest in health, a group of volunteer health professionals was recruited to collect the Italian national daily newspapers and weekly magazines listed in the Italian [Accertamenti Diffusione Stampa] certification, published over a sample one-week period. Sport newspapers were excluded from collection. The week was selected randomly: daily newspapers were collected from the 25th to the 31st of May 2008, whereas weekly magazines were collected during the following week (1–7 June 2008). [...] Volunteers, that were blind to the aim of the study, were then asked to perform a first rough article selection, by collecting from each newspaper all stories dealing with any kind of health-related topic. If the newspaper or magazine under review had an enclosed supplement on health, the instruction was to select it all. Then, one researcher (LI) performed the final selection, by specifically picking out, among the articles gathered by the volunteers, those properly meeting with the definition of health science communication articles [...] Identical health science communication articles reported in different newspapers were counted as one." (p. 2)
Johansen et al. 1996	["The objective of this study was thus to assess the reliability of health-related articles in the newspapers and of the information handed out at The Health Fair 1995"] (p. 260)	Aftenposten, VG, Dagbladet, Vårt Land, Adresseavisen and Nordlys (newspapers) (p. 260)	<i>Inclusion:</i> ["«All material that was referring to or informing about health was picked out.»"] (p. 260) <i>Exclusion:</i> ["«We only included editorially prepared content, not advertisements or letters to the editor.»"] (p. 260)	[«The newspapers were read thoroughly everyday.»] (p. 260)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Kininmonth et al. 2017	<p>“Therefore, the main aims of this study were to use the existing validated quality assessment tool by Robinson et al [reference] to assess the quality of nutrition coverage in particular in five of the highest circulating printed newspapers and to determine the most important predictors of article quality to explain any differences in article quality between papers.” (p. 2)</p>	<p>The Sun, The Daily Mirror, The Daily Mail, The Daily Express and The Daily Telegraph (newspapers) (p. 2)</p>	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> "Articles covering an aspect of nutrition (as an exposure) and an aspect of human health (as a health outcome) were identified." (p. 2)</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> “Articles were excluded if (A) they covered nutrition but without a related health outcome (eg, the use of cucumber as a beauty therapy) or (B) they covered a health outcome such as heart disease without discussing diet. Articles from opinion columns were also excluded." (p. 2)</p>	<p>"Printed editions of the five newspapers were collected on 6 days of the week (Monday–Saturday) for 6 weeks from 30 June 2014 to 9 August 2014. Sunday was excluded from the data collection as a pilot study revealed repetition of nutrition/health articles from previous days. Each printed newspaper was scanned by a researcher in its entirety [...] This process was carried out in duplicate and independently by a second researcher, and the selected articles were reviewed by a third nutritionist." (p. 2)</p>
Krauth and Apollonio 2015	<p>"Our goal was to determine whether popular reporting accurately reflects findings from the scientific literature on tobacco cessation treatment for ADM populations in treatment." (p. 1)</p>	<p>Newspaper and magazine reports via LexisNexis (p. 2)</p>	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> "Published in English" (p. 2)</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> “Sources discussing smoking cessation therapy in [abuse and mental health] populations that assessed only non-smoking related health outcomes" (p. 2)</p>	<p>"Studies were screened in two stages, as outlined in figure 1. Any articles or websites that did not clearly meet the criteria were discussed by two authors (DA and DK) for a final decision about inclusion." (p. 2-3)</p>

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Lewis et al. 2010	<p>“The objective of the study was to measure the scientific quality of Australian newspaper media reports about two international peer-reviewed research papers reporting results on complementary medicines published in biomedical journals during Feb/March 2007.” (p. 57)</p>	<p>The Australian, The Sydney Morning Herald, The Daily Telegraph, Herald Sun, The Age, MX Melbourne, The Advertiser, The Mercury, The West Australian, Northern Territory News, Sunday Territorian, The Courier Mail, The Canberra Times (p. 61)</p>	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> Report on either the "Antioxidant study" or the "Prenatal Multivitamin Study" (p. 60)</p>	<p>"Factiva was used to identify articles reporting on the ‘Antioxidant Study’ published in JAMA [...] using the generic search terms ‘vitamins’ and ‘antioxidants’ [...] A press release about the ‘Antioxidant Study’ was obtained from JAMA by email request. A press release was not prepared by the journal CPT for the ‘Prenatal Multivitamin Study’. Articles about the Prenatal Multivitamin Study published in CPT were then identified from mainstream newspapers and the newswire in a separate Factiva search using the terms ‘prenatal supplement’ and ‘pregnancy and multivitamin’" (p. 60)</p>
Motl et al. 2005	<p>“In this pilot project, we explored the quality of health-related news reports in the mass media. The existing CONSORT guidelines were modified to determine the completeness and accuracy of reports of medical research in the print and electronic news media when compared with the original research articles.” (p. 721)</p>	<p>USA Today, and The Wall Street Journal (newspapers), MSNBC (www.msnbc.com) and CNN General News (www.cnn.com) (Television), and Time, and Newsweek (Magazines) (p. 722)</p>	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> "Of the retrieved releases, only health reports discussing completed RCTs were included." (p. 722)</p>	<p>"USA Today, the Wall Street Journal, MSNBC, and CNN were accessed daily and Time and Newsweek were accessed weekly from October 1, 2002, through December 31, 2002. All media releases in each news source regarding recently published health-related studies were retrieved." (p. 722)</p>

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Moynihan et al. 2000	Not stated explicitly	Los Angeles Times, New York Times, Washington Post, USA Today, Chicago Sun-Times, Columbus Dispatch, Denver Post, Denver Rocky Mountain News, Detroit News, Indianapolis Star, Kansas City Star, Milwaukee Journal Sentinel, Omaha World-Herald, Cleveland Plain Dealer, St. Louis Post-Dispatch, Minneapolis Star Tribune, Atlanta Journal-Constitution, Baltimore Sun, Boston Globe, Boston Herald, Buffalo News, New York Daily News, Pittsburgh Post-Gazette, Louisville Courier-Journal, Houston Chronicle, St. Petersburg Times, Tampa Tribune, New Orleans Times-Picayune, Arizona Republic, Phoenix Gazette, Sacramento Bee, San Diego Tribune, San Francisco Chronicle, and Seattle Time (newspapers) via Lexis-Nexis, Wall Street Journal and Miami Herald (newspapers) via a library, and ABC, CBS, NBC, and CNN via The Vanderbilt Television News Archive Evening News database (p. 1646-5)	<i>Exclusion:</i> "Newspaper and television stories were excluded if they emphasized another topic, with only a brief mention of the study drug (146 stories); were in a "question and answer" or "Dear Doctor" format (37 stories); dealt solely with business issues (17 stories); concerned indications other than those listed (12 stories); were letters to the editor or corrections, or lacked sufficient information (17 stories); or did not cover the study drug at all (55 stories; e.g., stories on "super aspirin" referring to other antiplatelet drugs)." (p. 1646)	"The key words used in the search strategy were "osteoporosis" and additional terms "alendronate or Fosamax" for alendronate; "cholesterol" and additional terms "pravastatin or Pravachol" for pravastatin; and "heart" and "aspirin" for aspirin [...] A systematic probability sample of 60 newspaper stories for each drug 32 was obtained from the complete list of stories on each drug, ordered according to date and divided into 60 equal-sized blocks. Using a random starting point in each block, we reviewed the stories for content, excluding each story that met the exclusion criteria listed below and substituting the next story from the block [...] The Vanderbilt Television News Archive Evening News data base was used to obtain videotaped stories on ABC, CBS, and NBC nightly network [...] Search strategies similar to those used for newspaper articles were employed." (p. 1646)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Nichols and Chase 2005	<p>"Clearly, the local daily newspapers can be an ally or foe in the moral and strategic vision of promoting and fostering healthier societies. It is therefore crucial for stakeholders in the health sector to analyse and monitor on a continuous basis the scientific quality of health-related reports in the news- print medium to ensure accuracy, completeness, and a balanced view of articles published [references]. The authors therefore undertook analyses of the scientific quality of the information contained in health research articles published in the three local daily newspapers namely: the Trinidad and Tobago Newsday (Newsday), The Trinidad Express (Express), and The Trinidad Guardian (Guardian)." (p. 303)</p>	<p>The Trinidad and Tobago Newsday, The Trinidad Express, and The Trinidad Guardian (newspapers) (p. 303)</p>	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> "Articles were included in the study if they were press released from peer-reviewed journals, sourced from an international news agency (eg Reuters, Associated Press etc), published in magazines and bulletins or written by local journalists." (p. 303)</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> "Editorials, commentaries, articles for debate and education, narrative reviews, letters to the editor, case reports and articles related to the local health sector and advertisement of health products and services were excluded." (p. 303)</p>	<p>"A search was done of all issues of the daily (ie [sic] newspapers with publications on four or more days of the week) and weekend publications of the Newsday, Express and Guardian." (p. 303)</p>

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Rabi et al. 2009	“The objective of this study was to review the content of lay media articles to determine how risk was communicated to the public.” (p. 2)	Factiva (p. 2)	<p><i>Inclusion:</i> "Articles were eligible for inclusion if they discussed heart or cardiovascular disease OR safety, AND rosiglitazone." (p. 2)</p> <p><i>Exclusion:</i> Articles were excluded if they did not address the safety of rosiglitazone, or if the article's primary focus was on the impact of the Nissen article on rosiglitazone's manufacturer's (GlaxoSmithKline) stock prices." (p. 2)</p>	"A search strategy was developed in consultation with an academic librarian to ensure capture of all potentially relevant articles. Factiva indexing makes simple keyword searches most effective and we identified all articles containing the keywords "rosiglitazone" or "Avandia" [...] This search was restricted to English language articles [...] Two reviewers (DMR, GB) screened full text articles for eligibility" (p. 2)
Robinson et al. 2013	"This study aimed to assess a cross-section of all of the newspaper articles related to health published over a 2-month period in order to explore factors which may be associated with good and poor reporting, and to explore the newspapers' sources of their stories and the differing editorial styles." (p. 40)	The Sun, The Daily Mirror, The Daily Mail, The Daily Express, The Times, The Daily Telegraph, The Guardian, and The Independent (newspapers) (p. 40)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Each article pertaining to human health and medicine that reported newly emerging results was included" (p. 40)	"A selection of papers from each day was subsequently scanned by another author to ensure that any relevant articles were not missed. Features from the health supplements, often containing reviews, articles and plans for future research, were excluded" (p. 40)
Robinson et al. 2018	"The aim of our study is to evaluate New Zealand media articles on their coverage of key issues regarding health interventions and whether this is consistent with the best level of available evidence." (p. 925)	NZ Herald, Otago Daily Times, Stuff, TVNZ, TV3, 20/20 and 60 Minutes (p. 926)	<i>Exclusion:</i> "All articles that were not primarily about a health intervention were excluded. Intervention was defined as a medication, device or in-hospital procedure directed at patient health [...] Articles were not included if written by someone other than a journalist, for example, letters to the editor" (p. 926)	"The following search terms were utilised: 'Health/Treatment/Medication/Operation/Surgery/Intervention'. These terms were searched for together on each source's online archive and then individually in combination with the word 'Health.' [...] Articles were judged by three individual, randomly allocated assessors and excluded if a health intervention was not the primary theme for the majority of the article. If there was no unanimous decision, the article was discussed by a small group of five independent assessors." (p. 926)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Schwitzer 2008	Not stated explicitly	The “top 50 most widely circulated newspapers in the US”, TIME, Newsweek, and U.S. News & World Report (magazines) ABC, CBS, and NBC (TV) (p. 0700-1)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "In order to be eligible for review, a story must include a claim of efficacy or safety in a health care product or procedure (drug, device, diagnostic or screening test, surgical procedure, dietary recommendation, vitamin, supplement)." (p. 0701)	"HealthNewsReview.org monitors news coverage by the top 50 most widely circulated newspapers in the US; the most widely used wire service, the Associated Press; and the three leading newsweekly magazines—TIME, Newsweek, and U.S. News & World Report. Each weekday we watch the morning and evening newscasts of the three most watched television networks— ABC, CBS, and NBC." (p. 0701)
Smith et al. 2005	"To analyse the reviews of medical news articles posted on media doctor, a medical news-story monitoring website." (p. 190)	The Age, The Australian The Sydney Morning Herald, ABC news online, and ninemsn (p. 190)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Articles were eligible for inclusion if they were relevant to the management and prevention of disease in Australia, and particularly if they were related to claims about new treatments, procedures and diagnostic tests. Interventions must have been the subject of clinical research (or a claim to that effect made" (p. 190-191)	"Current news articles about medical treatments are identified by daily website searches." (p. 190)
Stassen 2016	“The aim of this research paper therefore is to analyse health news articles specifically pertaining to new medical research at six daily newspapers in South Africa to determine the standard of these reports, identify potential shortcomings, and suggest possible reformative steps that can be taken to improve the quality of health journalism at these newspapers.” (p. 13)	Die Burger, Business Day, Cape Argus, Cape Times, The New Age and The Times (newspapers) (p. 14)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "On" or "relating to" new medical research (p. 50)	"The articles were sourced from the health news archive of Stellenbosch University’s Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences (FMHS). This archive system, called 'Media Review', was updated daily by the FMHS Division of Marketing and Communications where a designated person manually searched newspapers and archived articles on all health-related issues, including new medical research [...] The daily searches were also supplemented by health-related news items picked up by the South African media monitoring service, Newsclip." (p. 50)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Sumner et al. 2014	"We aimed to clarify how often news contains claims or advice from health related research that go beyond those in the peer reviewed journal articles, and to identify the likely source of these exaggerations (press releases or news)." (p. 2)	Associated Press, BBC News, Daily Mail, Daily Star, Daily Star Sunday, Economist, Express, Financial Times, Guardian, Guardian.co.uk, Independent, Mail on Sunday, Mail Online, Metro, Mirror, New Scientist, Observer, People, Press Association, Racing Post, Reuters, Scotsman, Sun, Sunday Express, Sunday Mail, Sunday Mirror, Sunday Post, Sunday Sun, Sunday Telegraph, Sunday Times, Telegraph, and Times (Supplementary Information, p. 1)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Associated" with one of the press releases (p. 2)	"First, the key words of the press release were searched on the Nexis® database (http://www.lexisnexis.com/uk/nexis/). The search was limited to UK national newspapers and articles published within 30 days of the PR. Each search was performed several times with different key words, from specific to more general. For example, for the PR titled 'Scientists demonstrate potential new treatment for most common form of infant leukaemia', the search would be performed with key words 'BET proteins AND MLL', 'proteins AND leukaemia', 'new treatment AND leukaemia', and 'treatment AND cancer'. In the same way, BBC news webpages (http://www.bbc.co.uk/news/) and Reuters webpages (http://uk.reuters.com/) were searched. Finally, a google search was performed using the key words and the name of each individual newspaper. In cases where several news articles were found from the same newspaper, the longer article was selected for coding." (Supplementary Information, p. 1)
Sumner et al. 2016	Not stated explicitly	Nexis database, BBC.co.uk, uk.reuters.com, Google (p. 3)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "[Result from press releases] for studies published in the following journals, for the entire year of 2011: Lancet, British Medical Journal (BMJ), Science, Nature, Nature Neuroscience, Nature Immunology, Nature Medicine, and Nature Genetics" (p. 3)	"Searching the Nexis database, BBC.co.uk, uk.reuters.com, and by performing a Google search" (p. 3)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016	"The purpose of this study, therefore, was to determine whether news organizations have gotten better—or worse—in their reporting on important consumer health topics such as diets, drugs, medical devices, surgery, and other medical interventions." (p. 1)	USA Today, the Wall Street Journal's health blog, the New York Times, the Los Angeles Times, the Washington Post, the Chicago Tribune, the Houston Chronicle, the Arizona Republic, the Denver Post, and the Dallas Morning News (newspapers), National Public Radio, MSNBC.com, CNN.com, WebMD.com, the Associated Press, Reuters Health, and HealthDay (news websites), Time, Newsweek, and U.S. News & World Report (magazines), "the major network TV organizations", and "the top 100 daily newspapers by circulation" (p. 3)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Stories had to include a claim about the efficacy or safety of a health intervention and must have been posted on the news organization's website [...] The criteria used to decide which stories were selected for review included whether that news organization had been reviewed recently, which story's topic affected more people, and which reviewers were available [reference]" (p. 3); "[HealthNewsReview.org] reviewed only stories made available online." (p. 11)	"HealthNewsReview.org did not attempt to review all health stories published by any news organization or set of organizations, although it did follow systematic procedures in selecting stories to review." (p. 11)
Wilson et al. 2009	Not stated explicitly	The Daily Telegraph, Herald Sun, The Australian, Sydney Morning Herald, and The Age (newspapers), ABC Online and ninemsn (news websites), and "Today Tonight" Channel 7 and "A Current Affair" Channel 9 (TV) (p. 2)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "Stories are eligible for review if they cover new health interventions for humans, including drugs, surgical procedures, diagnostic tests, and complementary therapies." (p. 2)	"Stories are gathered by a researcher who systematically searches news internet [sic] sites where articles or transcripts are downloaded. Most of these sites have dedicated health pages. Sites without health pages are searched using stem keywords such as 'health', 'test', 'research', and 'study'." (p. 2)

Study	Objective	Sampling frame	Selection criteria	Selection technique
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006	"To examine media stories on research presented at scientific meetings to see if they reported basic study facts and cautions, and whether they were clear about the preliminary stage of the research" (p. 576)	USA Today, New York Times, Los Angeles Times, and Washington Post (newspapers), and TV and radio reports via LexisNexis, and the Wall Street Journal (newspaper) via ProQuest (p. 576-7)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "We included all news stories reporting on a single research presentation and stories reporting on more than one presentation if at least one of the presentations related to the story's headline." (p. 576)	"We identified media coverage of [...] five meetings in 2002–2003 (there was no International AIDS conference in 2003, so we included the 2002 meeting; all other meetings were held in 2003) by searching two media databases [...] We conducted full text searches with appropriate wildcards for combinations of phrases: (name of meeting) w/10 (scientific session OR conference OR meeting). (The 'w/10' parameter identifies news stories in which 'scientific session', 'conference' or 'meeting' appears within 10 words before or after the name of each meeting.) We identified media coverage of these five meetings in 2002–2003 (there was no International AIDS conference in 2003, so we included the 2002 meeting; all other meetings" (p. 576)
Yavchitz et al. 2012	"We aimed to (1) evaluate the presence of “spin” in press releases and associated media coverage and (2) evaluate whether findings of RCTs contained within press releases and media coverage are misinterpreted." (p. 2)	"General news” library of LEXIS-NEXIS (p. 2)	<i>Inclusion:</i> "All news related to the articles or press releases were retrieved" (p. 2)	"For all selected press releases, we systematically searched for related news items [...] using (1) the name of the disease; (2) the treatment being evaluated, and, if needed, the name of the first or second author. All news related to the articles or press releases were retrieved, and we selected the news that had the highest number of words dedicated to the selected study." (p. 2)

Appendix 4: Reported subgroup analyses (subgroups of news media reports)

Study	Factor
Andrew et al. 2016	Medium (p. 275)
Basu and Hogard 2008,	None
Bonevski et al. 2008	Media outlet (p. 3) Time period (p. 3) Category of complementary or alternative medicine (Table 2, p. 4) Clinical outcome category (Table 3, p. 4)
Bubela et al. 2008	Herbal vs. pharmaceutical clinical trial (subject) (Table 1)
Cassels et al. 2003	Drug (Tables 1-5, p. 1134-6)
Hackman and Moe 1999	Newspaper (Table 1, p. 1565)
Haneef et al. 2015	None
Heaner 2009	Newspaper (p. 135-9)
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002	Newspaper (Table 2, p. 1673) Medicine (Table 3, p. 1674)
Iaboli et al. 2010	None
Johansen et al. 1996	None
Kininmonth et al. 2017	Newspaper (Table 1, p. 3; Table 4, p. 6) Food category (Table 2, p. 4; Table 3, p. 5) Health category (Table 2, p. 4; Table 3, p. 5) Day (Table 3, p. 5) Named vs. unnamed reporter (Table 3, p. 5) Article size (Table 3, p. 5)
Krauth and Apollonio 2015	None
Lewis et al. 2010	Study (p. 62-7)
Motl et al. 2005	Medium (Table 1, p. 722) Newswire vs. non-newswire (Table 1, p. 722)
Moynihan et al. 2000	Drug (Table 2, p. 1648) Medium (Table 3, p. 1648)
Nichols and Chase 2005	Newspaper (Table 2, p. 304-5)
Rabi et al. 2009	None
Robinson et al. 2013	Newspaper (Table 1, p. 43) Broadsheet vs. mid-market tabloid vs. popular tabloid newspaper (p. 42) Named vs. unnamed reporter (p. 42) Specialist vs. non-specialist journal (p. 42) Impact factor of journal (p. 42) Length (p. 42)
Robinson et al. 2018	Word count (Figure 4, p. 928)
Schwitzer 2008	None
Smith et al. 2005	Outlet (Box 2, p. 192) Medium (Box 3, P. 192)
Stassen 2016	Newspaper (p. 59-66) Regional vs. national newspaper (p. 66)
Sumner et al. 2014	"Exaggeration" vs. no "exaggeration" in related press release (p. 3)
Sumner et al. 2016	"Exaggeration" vs. no "exaggeration" in related press release (p. 6)
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016	Medium and time period (Table 1, p. 5; Table 3, p. 8) Story topic and time period (Table 1, p. 5; Tables 4a-b, p. 9) Time period (Table 2, p. 6) Time period excluding TV (Table 2, p. 6)
Wilson et al. 2009	Medium (p. 3)

Study	Factor
	Time period (Table 2, p. 3)
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006	Conference (Boxes 3-4, p. 578)
	General vs. specialized journal (Tables 3-4, p. 6-7)
	Profit vs. non-profit or not reported funding source (Tables 3-4, p. 6-7)
	Small (<112) vs. large (\geq 112) sample size (Tables 3-4, p. 6-7)
Yavchitz et al. 2012	Drug vs. other experimental treatment (Tables 3-4, p. 6-7)
	All non-statistically “significant” vs. other results of primary outcome (Tables 3-4, p. 6-7)
	Authors of press release (Tables 3-4, p. 6-7)
	Spin in abstract conclusion (Tables 3-4, p. 6-7)

Appendix 5: Descriptions of development of tools

Tool (set of criteria)	Pilot	Inter-rater agreement (reliability)	Other evaluation	Description
Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	No	No	No	"[The] instrument, which has not been formally validated, is a variant of others [references]. The instruments on which ours was based have not been formally validated but have been peer reviewed [sic] and subsequently published in high-impact medical journals." (p. 270)
Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	No	No	No	"[We] used a standardized coding frame, a common method for analyzing media coverage [references] for clinical trials."
Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Yes	No	No	"A coding instrument was developed and pilot-tested" (p. 1137)
Hackman and Moe 1999 (original)	Yes	Yes	No	"The rating items [...] and sampling procedure were developed during a 1-month pilot study [...] The first investigator (E.M.H.) scored the articles. To evaluate the reliability of the scoring instrument, we selected every fourth newspaper article for the second investigator (G.L.M.) to evaluate. [...] We compared total score and score components using the X ² test and Cohen's K statistic."(p. 1564)
Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	Yes	No	No	"Two researchers (RH, IB) tested the form on a randomly selected sample of 10 news items by reading the referenced article and the content of the selected news items to extract specific information for spin." (p. 4)
Heaner 2009 (original)	Yes	Yes	Content validity	P. 83-96
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)	Yes	Yes	No	"[Coding guide earlier used in a similar American [sic] study [was] retrieved [reference]. These were revised and expanded to fit the national circumstances. The coding instrument was then used by two coders in a pilot study on less material, and adjusted in areas of low agreement"] (p. 1672)
Iaboli et al. 2010 (original)	No	No	No	Not provided
Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Yes	Yes	Sensibility	Oxman et al. 1993
Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	No	No	No	"Our rating instrument [...] is an extension of one previously used to assess the quality of medical news reporting in the US. [reference] We added criteria covering novelty of the treatment, availability, treatment options, presence of elements of 'disease mongering', [reference] and the reporting of evidence (study methodology)." (Smith et al. 2005, p. 191)

Tool (set of criteria)	Pilot	Inter-rater agreement (reliability)	Other evaluation	Description
Motl et al. 2005 (original)	Yes	Yes	No	“The CONSORT guidelines were modified to create a checklist to evaluate publications in the media regarding health studies [...] Independent reviewers validated the modified CONSORT checklist: three reviewers evaluated 10 media reports using the criteria. Results were compared and the checklist altered until the final scores of each reviewer fell within 5% of the mean score.” (p. 721-2)
Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)	No	No	No	Not provided
Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	No	No	No	Not provided
Rabi et al. 2009 (adapted from Cassels et al. 2008)	No	No	No	«We employed a quality of reporting checklist that was adapted from Cassels et al [reference].»
Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	Yes	No	No	“The Guidelines on Health and Science Communication 2001, published by the Royal Institution, Royal Society and the Social Issues Research Centre, [reference] were used as a starting point for development of the assessment tool, providing both stylistic and substantive guidance. [...] The quality assessment tool was piloted on 15 newspaper articles from the selected newspapers over 2 consecutive days. A number of criteria were subdivided with new criteria added, finally yielding a 22-item tool grouped into seven broad categories...” (p. 40)
Robinson et al. 2018 (original)	No	No	No	Not provided
Sumner et al. 2014 (original)	Yes	Yes	No	“[The coding template] was developed using a pilot batch of materials by iterative expansion and modification in order to capture aspects relevant to our main questions that were not adequately coded initially. Pilot testing was used to clarify potential ambiguity, and to solve coding difficulties and instances of low inter-rater reliability.”
Tabloid Analysis Tool	Yes	Yes	Validity	“A tool devised by Hackman and Moe [reference], and guidance issued by the Harvard School of Public Health and the International Food Information Council (IFIC) [reference] and the IFIC and the Institute of Food Technologists (IFT) [reference], provided some direction on elements for inclusion. [...] The TAT was piloted on ten test articles prior to the main study and was trialled by two impartial parties (registered dietitians) to ensure reliability and validity.” (p. 1125)
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	No	No	No	Not provided
Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)	Yes	No	No	“We developed a standardized data-abstraction form using previous work on the same topics [references] [...] The data-abstraction form was preliminarily tested by two of the reviewers with a sample of 15 press releases and original articles.”

Appendix 6: Criteria groups

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Group A: Criteria related to reporting on associations and randomization

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Bubela et al. 2008, Table 1	Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	“Randomization NOT specified”	Yes/No	1.3, 2.2
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Claiming a causal effect despite non-randomized study design”	Yes/No	1.3, 2.2
Heaner 2009, Appendix B, p. 198	Heaner 2009 (original)	“If findings correlational, does article imply causation?”	“Yes” “No” “Not applicable”	1.3, 2.2
Sumner et al. 2014, Supplementary Information, p. 2-3	Sumner et al. 2014 (original)	“Causal statements from correlational results”	“No relationship stated (but could have been)” “Statement of NO relationship/cause” “Statement of correlations” “Ambiguous statement of correlation/cause” “Conditional cause” “Can cause” “Causal statement”	1.3, 2.2
Sumner et al. 2016, Coding Sheet Guidelines, p. 6-7	Sumner et al. 2014	“Statement of cause”	“No relationship mentioned” “Statement of no relationship” “Statements of correlation” “Ambiguous statement of relationship” “Conditional statement of causation” “Statement of ‘can’” “Statements of causation”	1.3, 2.2
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, p. 577	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Relevant cautions provided about [...] controlled but not randomised studies”	Yes/No	1.3, 2.2
Yavchitz et al. 2012, Table 1, p. 5	Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)	“Focus on within-group (or over-all within) comparison”	Yes/No	1.3, 2.2

Group B: Criteria related to reporting on opinions

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Johansen et al. 1996, p. 261	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Opinions versus facts: Are facts clearly distinguished from opinions?	Five-point scale	1.6
Krauth and Apollonio 2015, p. 3-4	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Opinions versus Facts: Describes whether or not facts are clearly distinguished from opinions”	Five-point scale	1.6
Lewis et al. 2010, p. 61-2	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Opinion versus facts: Are facts clearly distinguished from opinions?”	Five-point scale	1.6
Basu and Hogard 2008, Appendix, p, 1131	Tabloid Analysis Tool (TAT)	“Any statements attributed to ‘experts’, ‘researchers’ or ‘studies’ that are unsubstantiated?”	“Yes”/“No”	1.6

Group C: Criteria related to reporting on conflicts of interest

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Rabi et al. 2009, Table 2	Rabi et al. 2009 (adapted from Cassels et al. 2008)	“If an expert was used, was there disclosure of potential conflict of interest?”	Yes/No	1.7
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	Funding source	“Not reported”/“Reported”	1.7
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	Industry ties	“Not reported”/“Reported”	1.7
Bubela et al. 2008, Table 1	Bubela et al. 2008 (Original)	“Source of funding NOT specified”	Yes/No	1.7
Schwitzer 2008, Table 1, p. 0702	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Seek independent sources and explore conflicts of interests in sources”	“Satisfactory”/Not	1.7
Stassen 2016, p. 51	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Does the story use independent sources and identify conflicts of interest?”	Yes/No	1.7
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 6	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Using independent sources and exploring source conflicts of interest”	“Satisfactory”/Not	1.7
Heaner 2009, Appendix B, p. 198	Heaner 2009 (original)	“Funding sources/potential conflicts of interest disclosed”	“Yes”/“No”	1.7
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002, Table 2, p. 1673	Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)	[“Inform about about connection”] to industry	Yes/No	1.7
Iaboli et al. 2010, Table 1, p. 3	Iaboli et al. 2010 (original)	“Are financial conflicts of interest mentioned?”	Yes/No	1.7

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 2, p. 927	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether sources of information and any known conflicts of interests of informants are disclosed”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	1.7
Moynihan et al. 2000, Table 2, p. 1648	Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)	“Disclosed tie [with industry]”	Yes/No	1.7

Group D: Criteria related to “disease mongering”

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Schwitzer 2008, Table 1, p. 0702	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review) (Media Doctor Australia)	“Avoid disease mongering”	“Satisfactory”/Not	1.9
Stassen 2016, p. 51	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Does the story commit disease mongering?”	Yes/No	1.9
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 6	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Avoiding disease mongering”	“Satisfactory”/Not	1.9
Bonevski et al. 2008, Table 4, p. 5	Media Doctor Australia	“Is there is evidence of ‘disease mongering’?”	“Satisfactory”/Not	1.9
Robinson et al. 2008, Table 2, p. 927	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether there is evidence of ‘disease mongering’”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	1.9
Smith et al. 2005, p. 191	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether there is evidence of ‘disease mongering’”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	1.9
Wilson et al. 2009, Table 1, p. 2	Media Doctor Australia	“Avoided elements of disease mongering”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	1.9

Group E: Criteria related to reporting on the need for comparisons

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Concluding a beneficial effect despite lack of comparator”	Yes/No	2.1
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 2, p. 927	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether there is evidence to support the treatment”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	2.1
Smith et al. 2005, p. 191	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether there is objective evidence to support the treatment”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	2.1
Wilson et al. 2009, Table 1, p. 2	Media Doctor Australia	“Reported evidence supporting the intervention”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	2.1
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, p. 577	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Relevant cautions provided about [...] uncontrolled studies”	Yes/No	2.1

Group F: Criteria related to reporting on blinding

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Bubela et al. 2008, Table 1	Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	“Double-blinding NOT specified”	Yes/No	2.4, 2.5, 2.6

Group G: Criteria related to reporting on loss to follow-up

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Bubela et al. 2008, Table 1	Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	“Withdrawals/dropouts NOT specified”	Yes/No	2.7

Group H: Criteria related to reporting on study design and risk of bias in general

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	“Study design”	“Not reported”/“Reported”	Unclear
Hackman and Moe 1999, Table 1, p. 1565	Hackman and Moe 1999 (original)	“Study design and analysis described”	“Containing variable”/Not	Unclear
Heaner 2009, Appendix B, p. 198	Heaner 2009 (original)	“Study design described?”	“Yes”/“No”	Unclear
Nichols and Chase, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	“Study design”	“Not stated” “Meta-analyses” “Experimental” “Cohort” “Case-control” “Survey”	Unclear
Basu and Hogard 2008, Appendix, p. 1131	Tabloid Analysis Tool (TAT)	“Study design stated or described?”	“Yes”/“No”	Unclear
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, Box 4, p. 587	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Study design”	“Explicitly stated” “Not stated (researchers could guess)” “Not stated (researchers could not guess)”	Unclear
Schwitzer 2008, Table 1, p. 0702	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Discuss quality of the evidence”	“Satisfactory”/Not	Unclear
Stassen 2016, p. 51	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Does the story seem to grasp the quality of the evidence?”	Yes/No	Unclear
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 6	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Discussing evidence quality”	“Satisfactory”/Not	Unclear
Bonevski et al. 2008, Table 4, p. 5	Media Doctor Australia	“Does the article report the type of evidence supporting the treatment?”	“Satisfactory”/Not	Unclear
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 1, p. 927	Robinson et al. 2018 (original)	“Discussion of evidence quality”	“Inclusion in media content”/not	Unclear
Johansen et al. 1996, p. 261	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Validity: Is the assessment of the credibility (validity) of the evidence clear and well-founded (not misleading)?	Five-point scale	Unclear
Krauth and Apollonio 2015, p. 3-4	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Validity: Describes whether or not the assessment of the credibility (validity) of the evidence is clear and well-founded (not misleading)”	Five-point scale	Unclear

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Lewis et al. 2010, p. 61-2	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Validity: Is the assessment of the credibility (validity) of the evidence clear and well-founded (not misleading)?”	Five-point scale	Unclear
Nichols and Chase 2005, Table 2, p. 305	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	“Validity/reliability of procedure addressed“	“No”/“Yes”	Unclear
Motl et al. 2005, Table 1, p. 722	Motl et al. 2005 (original)	“Are the results of the study interpreted correctly? Does this include limitations?”	Three-point scale	Unclear
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	“Study limitation(s)”	“Not reported”/“Reported”	Unclear
Hackman and Moe 1999, Table 1, p. 1565	Hackman and Moe 1999 (original)	“Limitations of study reported”	“Containing variable”/Not	Unclear
Heaner 2009, Appendix B, p. 198	Heaner 2009 (original)	“Are any limitations reported?”	“Yes”/“No”	Unclear
Nichols and Chase 2005, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	“Study procedure stated”	Yes/No	Unclear
Basu and Hogard 2008, Appendix, p. 1131	Tabloid Analysis Tool (TAT)	“Limitations of the study reported?”	“Yes”/“No”	Unclear

Group I: Criteria related to reporting on consistency between studies

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Johansen et al. 1996, p. 261	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Consistency: Is the consistency of the evidence (between studies) considered and is the assessment well-founded (not misleading)?	Five-point scale	2.8, 2.9, 3.5
Krauth and Apollonio 2015, p. 3-4	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Consistency: Describes whether or not the consistency of the evidence (between studies) is considered and whether the assessment is well-founded (not misleading)”	Five-point scale	2.8, 2.9, 3.5
Motl et al. 2005, Table 1, p. 722	Motl et al. 2005 (original)	“Are efforts made to interpret the results in the context of current evidence?”	Three-point scale	2.8, 2.9, 3.5
Kininmonth et al. 2017, Appendix 1 to Robinson et al. 2013	Robinson et al. 2013	“Does the article state whether the study differs from previous research?”	“Yes”/“No”	2.8
Robinson et al. 2013, Appendix 1	Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	“Does the article state whether the study differs from previous research?”	“Yes”/“No”	2.8

Group J: Criteria related to reporting on the play of chance

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Johansen et al. 1996, p. 261	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Precision: Is there a clear and well-founded (not misleading) assessment of the precision of any estimates that are reported or of the probability that any of the reported findings might be due to chance?	Five-point scale	2.15, 2.16
Krauth and Apollonio 2015, p. 3-4	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Precision: Describes whether or not the author provides a clear and well-founded (not misleading) assessment of the precision of any estimates that are reported or of the probability that any of the reported findings might be due to chance”	Five-point scale	2.15, 2.16
Lewis et al. 2010, p. 61-2	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Precision: Is there a clear and well-founded (not misleading) assessment of the precision of any estimates that are reported or of the probability that any of the reported findings might be due to chance?”	Five-point scale	2.15, 2.16
Motl et al. 2005, Table 1, p. 722	Motl et al. 2005 (original)	“Is the sample size clearly described?”	Three-point scale	2.15
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	“# Patients”	“Not reported”/“Reported”	2.15
Bubela et al. 2008, Table 1	Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	“Sample size NOT specified”	Yes/No	2.15
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Claiming a beneficial effect despite small sample size not reported”	Yes/No	2.15
Nichols and Chase 2005, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	“Number of participants stated”	Yes/No	2.15
Kininmonth et al. 2017, Appendix 1 to Robinson et al. 2013	Robinson et al. 2013	“Does the article state the number of subjects?”	“Yes”/“No”	2.15
Robinson et al. 2013, Appendix 1	Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	“Does the article state the number of subjects?”	“Yes”/“No”	2.15
Basu and Hogard 2008, Appendix, p. 1131	Tabloid Analysis Tool (TAT)	“Sample size reported?”	“Yes”/“No”	2.15
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, Box 4, p. 587	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Study size reported?”	Yes/No	2.15
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, p. 577	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Relevant cautions provided about [...] small (human) studies”	Yes/No	2.15

Group K: Criteria related to qualitative descriptions of effects

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Stassen 2016, p. 51	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Does the story adequately explain/quantify the harms of the intervention?”	Yes/No	1.1, 3.6, New 2.3a
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 4, p. 1135	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Quantification of benefits	“Absolute” “Relative” “Both absolute and relative” “No quantitative information”	2.13, New 2.3a
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 4, p. 1135	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Quantifications of harms	“Absolute” “Relative” “Both absolute and relative” “No quantitative information”	2.13, New 2.3a
Moynihan et al. 2000, Table 3, p. 1648	Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)	Quantification of benefits	“Did not quantify benefits” “Quantified benefits”	New 2.3a
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Linguistic spin or hype”	Yes/No	New 2.3a
Schwitzer 2008, Table 1, p. 0702	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Quantify benefits”	“Satisfactory”/Not	New 2.3a
Schwitzer 2008, Table 1, p. 0702	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Quantify harms”	“Satisfactory”/Not	New 2.3a
Stassen 2016, p. 51	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Does the story adequately quantify the benefits of the treatment/test/product/procedure?”	Yes/No	New 2.3a
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 6	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Quantifying harms”	“Satisfactory”/Not	New 2.3a
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 6	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Quantifying benefits”	“Satisfactory”/Not	New 2.3a
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002, Table 2, p. 1673	Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)	[“Quantify effect”]	Yes/No	New 2.3a
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002, Table 2, p. 1673	Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)	[“Use exaggerated terms”]	Yes/No	New 2.3a
Wilson et al. 2009, Table 1, p. 2	Media Doctor Australia	“Quantified the benefits of intervention”	“Satisfactory”	New 2.3a

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
			“Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	
Nichols and Chase, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	“Results quantified”	“No”/“Yes”	New 2.3a
Kininmonth et al. 2017, Appendix 1 to Robinson et al. 2013	Robinson et al. 2013	“Does the article state that a ‘breakthrough’ has been made, or a ‘cure’ been found?”	“Yes”/“No”	New 2.3a
Robinson et al. 2013, Appendix 1	Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	“Does the article state that a ‘breakthrough’ has been made, or a ‘cure’ been found?”	“Yes”/“No”	New 2.3a
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, Box 4, p. 578	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Study results quantified”	Yes/No	New 2.3a
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 2, p. 927	Media Doctor Australia	“How the benefits of the treatment are framed”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	New 2.3a

Group L: Criteria related to selective reporting in news reports

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Selective reporting of outcomes favoring statistically significant results”	Yes/No	2.11, 2.17
Yavchitz et al. 2012, Table 1, p. 5	Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)	“Focus on positive secondary outcome”	Yes/No	2.11

Group M: Criteria related to reporting on subgroup analyses

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Yavchitz et al. 2012, Table 1, p. 5	Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)	“Focus on inappropriate subgroup”	Yes/No	2.12

Group N: Criteria related to reporting absolute risk

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, Box 4, p. 578	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“At least one absolute risk reported”	Yes/No	2.13
Robinson et al. 2013, Appendix 1	Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	“Does the article report the absolute risk?”	“Yes”/“No”	2.13
Kininmonth et al. 2017, Appendix 1 to Robinson et al. 2013	Robinson et al. 2013	“Does the article report the absolute risk?”	“Yes”/“No”	2.13
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	“Outcomes/benefits”	"Relative" "Absolute" "Relative + Absolute"	2.13
Bonevski et al. 2008, Table 4, p. 5	Media Doctor Australia	“How are the benefits of the treatment framed (in relative and absolute terms)?”	“Satisfactory”/Not	2.13
Iaboli et al. 2010, Table 1, p. 3	Iaboli et al. 2010 (original)	“Are benefits reported in relative or absolute terms?”	Absolute/Relative	2.13
Moynihan et al. 2000, Table 3, p. 1648	Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)	“Quantified benefits”	“Only relative benefits” “Only absolute benefits” “Relative and absolute benefits”	2.13
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 4, p. 1135	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Quantification of benefits	“Absolute” “Relative” “Both absolute and relative” “No quantitative information”	2.13, New 2.3a
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 4, p. 1135	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Quantification of harms	“Absolute” “Relative” “Both absolute and relative” “No quantitative information”	2.13, New 2.3a

Group O: Criteria related to reporting on a lack of evidence

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Yavchitz et al. 2012, Table 1, p. 5	Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)	“Claiming equivalence when results failed to demonstrate a statistically significant difference”	Yes/No	2.18

Group P: Criteria related to reporting on options

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Bonevski et al. 2008, Table 4, p. 5	Media Doctor Australia	“Are alternative treatment options mentioned?”	“Satisfactory”/Not	New 3.1a
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 5, p. 1136	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Mention of drug alternatives	Yes/No	New 3.1a
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 5, p. 1136	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Mention of nondrug alternatives	Yes/No	New 3.1a
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 2, p. 927	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether alternative treatment options are mentioned”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	New 3.1a
Schwitzer 2008, Table 1, p. 0702	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Discuss existing alternative options”	“Satisfactory”/Not	New 3.1a
Smith et al. 2005, p. 191	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether alternative treatment options are mentioned”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	New 3.1a
Stassen 2016, p. 51	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Does the story compare the new approach with existing alternatives?”	Yes/No	New 3.1a
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 6	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Discussing alternatives”	“Satisfactory”/Not	New 3.1a
Wilson et al. 2009, Table 1, p. 2	Media Doctor Australia	“Described the treatment or diagnostic options that are available”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	New 3.1a

Group Q: Criteria related to reporting on animal studies

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Results of animal study to human application”	Yes/No	3.2
Kininmonth et al. 2017, Appendix 1 to Robinson et al. 2013	Robinson et al. 2013	“Does the article generalize from laboratory-based/animal studies to humans without explicitly stating so?”	“Yes”/“No”	3.2
Robinson et al. 2013, Appendix 1	Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	“Does the article generalize from laboratory-based/animal studies to humans without explicitly stating so?”	“Yes”/“No”	3.2
Sumner et al. 2014, Supplementary Information, p. 3	Sumner et al. 2014 (original)	“Human conclusions from non-human studies”	“Explicitly human” “Implicitly human” “Non-human primates” “Rodents” “Other animals/organisms” “Cells <i>in vitro</i> ” “Simulations”	3.2
Sumner et al. 2016, Coding Sheet Guidelines, p. 20-1	Sumner et al. 2014	Human conclusions from non-human studies	“Explicitly human” “Implicitly human” “Non-human primates” “Rodents” “Other beastsies” “Cells, In Vivo” “Simulations” “Other / More Than one” “Sample not explicit”	3.2
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, p. 577	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Relevant cautions provided about [...] animal/lab studies”	Yes/No	3.2

Group R: Criteria related to extrapolations from one (human) population, intervention or outcome to another

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Yavchitz et al. 2012, Table 1, p. 5	Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)	“Inappropriate extrapolation”	Yes/No	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4
Bubela et al. 2008, Table 1	Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	“Duration of the clinical trial NOT specified”	Yes/No	3.1
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 2, p. 1134	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Type of benefit reported	“Clinical” “Cost” “Surrogate”	3.1
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 2, p. 1134	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	“No. (and %) of articles mentioning only surrogate benefits”	Yes/No	3.1
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 3, p. 1135	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	“Type of harm; no. (and %) of mentions of harms”	“Clinical” “Surrogate”	3.1
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Study outcomes to different outcomes”	Yes/No	3.1
Nichols and Chase, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	“Outcome measures stated”	“No”/“Yes”	3.1
Nichols and Chase, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	“Duration of study stated”	“No”/“Yes”	3.1
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, Box 4, p. 578	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Follow-up time reported”	Yes/No	3.1
Motl et al. 2005, Table 1, p. 722	Motl et al. 2005 (original)	“Is the study population clearly described?”	Three-point scale	3.2
Motl et al. 2005, Table 1, p. 722	Motl et al. 2005 (original)	“Is the external validity correctly presented?”	Three-point scale	3.2
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	“Study population”	“Not reported”/“Reported”	3.2
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	“Exclusion criteria”	“Not reported”/“Reported”	3.2
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 5, p. 1136	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Mention of indications	Yes/No	3.2
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 5, p. 1136	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Mention of contraindications	Yes/no	3.2
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Study participants to larger or different population”	Yes/No	3.2
Heaner 2009, Appendix B, p. 198	Heaner 2009 (original)	“Correctly implies if sample is generalizable?”	“Yes”/“No”	3.2

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Johansen et al. 1996, p. 261	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Applicability: Is it clear to whom the information in the report applies?	Five-point scale	3.2
Krauth and Apollonio 2015, p. 3-4	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Applicability: Describes whether or not the author clarifies to whom the information in the report applies”	Five-point scale	3.2
Lewis et al. 2010, p. 61-2	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Applicability: Is it clear to whom the information in the report applies?”	Five-point scale	3.2
Nichols and Chase, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	“Characteristics of participants stated”	Yes/No	3.2
Kininmonth et al. 2017, Appendix 1 to Robinson et al. 2013	Robinson et al. 2013	“Is the study representative of the UK population, or does the article state that the results cannot be generalized?”	“Yes”/“No”	3.2
Robinson et al. 2013, Appendix 1	Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	“Is the study representative of the UK population, or does the article state that the results cannot be generalized?”	“Yes”/“No”	3.2
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 1, p. 927	Robinson et al. 2018 (original)	“Therapeutic indications”	“Inclusion in media content”/not	3.2
Basu and Hogard 2008, Appendix, p. 1131	Tabloid Analysis Tool (TAT)	“Study population reported?”	“Yes”/“No”	3.2
Basu and Hogard 2008, Appendix, p. 1131	Tabloid Analysis Tool (TAT)	“Characteristics of the population reported fully?”	“Yes”/“No”	3.2
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, Box 4, p. 578	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	“Subjects studied explicitly stated”	Yes/No	3.2
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	“Comparator”	“Not reported”/“Reported”	3.3
Bubela et al. 2008, Table 1	Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	“Dose NOT specified”	Yes/No	3.3
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Study intervention to different interventions”	Yes/No	3.3
Schwitzer 2008, Table 1, p. 0702	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Discuss availability of the new approach”	“Satisfactory”/Not	3.3
Stassen 2016, p. 52	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	Does the story establish the availability of the treatment/test/product/procedure?	Yes/No	3.3
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 6	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Discussing availability of the new approach”	“Satisfactory”/Not	3.3
Bonevski et al. 2008, Table 4, p. 5	Media Doctor Australia	“Does the article report the availability of the treatment in Australia?”	“Satisfactory”/Not	3.3

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 2, p. 927	Media Doctor Australia	“The availability of the treatment in NZ”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	3.3
Smith et al. 2005, p. 191	Media Doctor Australia	“The availability of the treatment in Australia”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	3.3
Wilson et al. 2009, Table 1, p. 2	Media Doctor Australia	“Reported the availability of the intervention”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	3.3
Nichols and Chase, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	Study setting stated	“No”/“Yes”	3.3
Nichols and Chase, Table 2, p. 304	Nichols and Chase 2005 (original)	Study Location stated	“No”/“Yes”	3.3
Basu and Hogard 2008, Appendix, p. 1131	Tabloid Analysis Tool (TAT)	“Would the average adult/relevant population group be reasonably expected/advised to consume this amount?”	“Yes”/“No”	3.3
Bubela et al. 2008, Table 1	Bubela et al. 2008 (original)	“Location of trial NOT specified”	Yes/No	3.4

Group S: Criteria related to reporting on advantages and disadvantages

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Stassen 2016	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Does the story adequately explain/quantify the harms of the intervention?”	Yes/No	1.1, 3.6, New 2.3a
Motl et al. 2005, Table 1, p. 722	Motl et al. 2005 (original)	“How well are the adverse events presented?”	Three-point scale	1.1, 3.6
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	“Adverse events”	“Not reported”/“Reported”	1.1, 3.6
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 1, p. 1134	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	“Mentioning at least one harm”	Yes/No	1.1, 3.6
Haneef et al. 2015, Table 2, p. 8	Haneef et al. 2015 (original)	“Not reporting of adverse events”	Yes/No	1.1, 3.6

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002, Table 2, p. 1673	Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)	["Mentions side-effect"]	Yes/No	1.1, 3.6
Iaboli et al. 2010, Table 1, p. 3	Iaboli et al. 2010 (original)	Are risks discussed?	Yes/No	1.1, 3.6
Bonevski et al. 2008, Table 4, p. 5	Media Doctor Australia	"Are harms of the treatment mentioned?"	"Satisfactory"/Not	1.1, 3.6
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 2, p. 927	Media Doctor Australia	"Whether harms of the treatment are mentioned"	"Satisfactory" "Not satisfactory" "Not applicable"	1.1, 3.6
Smith et al. 2005, p. 191	Media Doctor Australia	"Whether harms of the treatment are mentioned"	"Satisfactory" "Not satisfactory" "Not applicable"	1.1, 3.6
Wilson et al. 2009, Table 1, p. 2	Media Doctor Australia	"Described harms of intervention"	"Satisfactory" "Not satisfactory" "Not applicable"	1.1, 3.6
Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)	Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)	"Adverse effects mentioned"	Yes/No	1.1, 3.6
Kininmonth et al. 2017, Appendix 1 to Robinson et al. 2013	Robinson et al. 2013	"Does the article explore the safety of the intervention?"	"Yes"/"No"	1.1, 3.6
Robinson et al. 2013, Appendix 1	Robinson et al. 2013 (original)	"Does the article explore the safety of the intervention?"	"Yes"/"No"	1.1, 3.6
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 1, p. 927	Robinson et al. 2018 (original)	"Potential risks of harm "	"Inclusion in media content"/Not	1.1, 3.6
Woloshin and Schwartz 2006, p. 577	Woloshin and Schwartz 2006 (original)	"Were possible downsides noted for intervention studies?"	Yes/No	1.1, 3.6
Yavchitz et al. 2012, Table 1, p. 5	Yavchitz et al. 2012 (original)	"Ignored data of safety"	Yes/No"	1.1, 3.6
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	"Outcomes/benefits"	"Not reported"/"Reported"	3.6
Andrew et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 273	Andrew et al. 2016 (original)	"Costs"	"Not reported"/"Reported"	3.6
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 1, p. 1134	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	"Mentioning at least one benefit"	Yes/No	3.6

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Cassels et al. 2003, Table 5, p. 1136	Cassels et al. 2003 (original)	Mention of costs	Yes/No	3.6
Schwitzer 2008, Table 1, p. 0702	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Discuss costs”	“Satisfactory”/Not	3.6
Stassen 2016, p. 52	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Does the story adequately discuss the cost of the intervention?”	Yes/No	3.6
Walsh-Childers et al. 2016, Table 2, p. 6	Media Doctor Australia (Health News Review)	“Discussing costs”	“Satisfactory”/Not	3.6
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002, Table 2, p. 1673	Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)	[“Mention cost”]	Yes/No	3.6
Høye and Hjortdahl 2002, Table 2, p. 1673	Høye and Hjortdahl 2002 (adapted from Moynihan et al. 2000)	[“Discusses publicly subsidized prescription”]	Yes/No	3.6
Iaboli et al. 2010, Table 1, p. 3	Iaboli et al. 2010 (original)	Are costs discussed?	Yes/No	3.6
Johansen et al. 1996, p. 261	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Magnitude: Is the strength or magnitude of the findings (effects, risks, or costs) that are the main focus of the article clearly reported?	Five-point scale	3.6
Johansen et al. 1996, p. 261	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Consequences: Are all of the important consequences (benefits, risks and costs) of concern relative to the central topic of the report identified?	Five-point scale	3.6
Krauth and Apollonio 2015, p. 3-4	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Magnitude: Describes whether or not the strength or magnitude of the findings (effects, risks, or costs) that are the main focus of the article are clearly reported	Five-point scale	3.6
Krauth and Apollonio 2015, p. 3-4	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	Consequences: Describes whether or not all of the important consequences (benefits, risks, and costs) of concern relative to the central topic of the report are identified	Five-point scale	3.6
Lewis et al. 2010, p. 61-2	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Magnitude: Is the strength or magnitude of the findings (effects, risks, or costs) that are the main focus of the article clearly reported?”	Five-point scale	3.6
Lewis et al. 2010, p. 61-2	Index of Scientific Quality (ISQ)	“Consequences: Are all of the important consequences (benefits, risks and costs) of concern relative to the central topic of the report identified?”	Five-point scale	3.6
Bonevski et al. 2008, Table 4, p. 5	Media Doctor Australia	“Are costs of the treatment mentioned?”	“Satisfactory”/Not	3.6

Citation	Tool	Criterion	Response options	Relevant IHC Key Concepts
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 2, p. 927	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether the costs of the treatment are mentioned”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	3.6
Smith et al. 2005, p. 191	Media Doctor Australia	“Whether costs of the treatment are mentioned”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	3.6
Wilson et al. 2009, Table 1, p. 2	Media Doctor Australia	“Reported costs of intervention”	“Satisfactory” “Not satisfactory” “Not applicable”	3.6
Moynihan et al. 2000, Table 3, p. 1648	Moynihan et al. 2000 (original)	“Costs mentioned”	Yes/No	3.6
Robinson et al. 2018, Table 1, p. 927	Robinson et al. 2018 (original)	“Potential benefits”	“Inclusion in media content”/Not	3.6